

DRIVE

Demand Response Integration tEchnologies:

Unlocking the demand response potential in the distribution grid

Project H2020 n° 774431

D2.1 Requirements: Context of Application

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Deliverable nature:	Report (R)
Dissemination level: (Confidentiality)	Public (PU)
Contractual delivery date:	31 January 2018 (M2)
Actual delivery date:	07 February 2018 (M3)
Version:	1.0
Total number of pages:	83
Keywords:	Demand Response, Smart Grid, Smart Building, Distribution System Operator, Model Predictive Control, Multi-Agent Systems and Cyber-security.

Abstract

Increasing flexibility is key for the reliable operation of future power systems with very high penetration levels of Variable Renewable Energy Sources (VRES). In this scenario, the most significant source of flexibility is Demand Response (DR).

The DRiVE project intends to develop and validate a fully-integrated ICT infrastructure consisting of interoperable DR-enabling energy management solutions for residential and tertiary buildings and a platform for effective and secure management of flexibility at the level of the distribution grid.

This report discusses the various aspects of the technology upon which the DRiVE development will build. The DRiVE solution should comply with both legacy building automation protocols and emerging smart grid communication and cyber-security standards. It should also include extended capabilities of state-of-the-art forecasting and optimisation algorithms and have a user interface attractive enough to engage end-users into modifying consuming habits.

Document Information

IST Project Number	H2020 - 774431	Acronym	DRIVE
Full Title	Demand Response Integration tEchnologies: Unlocking the demand response potential in the distribution grid		
Project URL	http://www.r2msolution.com/2017/12/12/new-project-drive/		
Document URL	http://www.h2020-drive.eu/		
EU Project Officer	Francesco Liberati		
Acknowledgement	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under Grant Agreement n° 774431.		

Deliverable	Number	D2.1	Title	Requirements: Context of Application
Work Package	Number	WP2	Title	Specification, Requirements and ICT infrastructure design

Date of Delivery	Contractual	M2	Actual	M3
Status	version 1.0		Final	
Nature	report			
Dissemination level	public			

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Version Log			
Issue Date	Rev. No.	Author	Change
18 December 2017	0.1	A. Paiz (COMSA)	Template for contributions
16 January 2018	0.2	All	First draft
22 January 2018	0.3	R. Denysiuk (CEA) M. Vinyals (CEA) M. Mourshed (CU)	First review
2 February 2018	0.4	All	Answers to review
5 February 2018	0.5	R. Denysiuk (CEA) M. Mourshed (CU)	Second review
7 February 2018	0.6	A. Paiz (COMSA)	Final draft
8 February 2018	1.0	M.F. Robbe (CEA)	Final review by the coordinator

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

AAA	Authentication, authorisation and accounting
ADMM	Alternating direction method of multipliers
AGR	Aggregator
AHU	Air handling unit
AMQP	Advanced message queuing protocol
ANN	Artificial neural network
API	Application programming interface
BEIS	Department for Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy (UK government)
BEMS	Building energy management system
BMS	Building management system
BRP	Balance responsible party
CEN	European Committee for Standardisation
CENELEC	European Committee for Electrical Standardisation
CHP	Combined heat & power
CI	Computational intelligence
DER	Distributed energy resources
DG	Distributed generation
DMZ	Demilitarised zone
DNO	Distribution network operator
DR	Demand response
DRiVe	Demand response integration technologies
DSO	Distribution system operator
DSR	Demand-side response (used as synonym of DR, especially in UK)
EDR	Emergency demand response
EMS	Energy management system
EPBD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EU	European Union
EV	Electric vehicle
EVCS	Electric vehicle charging station
FCR	Frequency containment reserve
FDR	Fast demand response
FL	Fuzzy logic

GA	Generic algorithm
GDPR	General data protection regulation
GUI	Graphical user interface
HMI	Human – machine interface
HV	High-voltage
HVAC	Heating, ventilation and air conditioning
IACS	Industrial automation control system
ICT	Information and communication technologies
IED	Intelligent electronic device
IoT	Internet of things
ISO	International Organisation for Standardisation
IT	Information technology
LAN	Local area network
LEG	Local energy gateway
LPP	Large power producer
MAS	Multi-agent system
MPC	Model predictive control
OFGEM	Office of Gas & Electricity Markets (UK government)
OpenADR	Open automated demand response
OS	Operative System
PC	Personal computer
PI	Proportional-integrative
PID	Proportional-integrative-derivative
PV	Photovoltaic
RTO	Research and technology organisation
SaaS	Software-as-a-service
SCADA	Supervisory control and data acquisition
SGAM	Smart grid architecture model
SGIS	Smart grid information security
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprise
SVM	Support vector machine
ToU	Time of use
TSO	Transmission system operator
USEF	Universal Smart Energy Framework
V2G	Vehicle-to-grid

VAR	Volt-Ampere Reactive
Volt-VAR control	Process of managing voltage levels and reactive power
VPN	Virtual private network
VRES	Variable renewable energy sources
VRV	Variable refrigerant volume
VSD	Variable speed drive
WP	Work package

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 THE CONTEXT OF DEMAND RESPONSE

It is widely recognised that increasing flexibility is key for the reliable operation of future power systems with very high penetration levels of variable renewable energy sources (VRES) [1]. Flexibility is the ability of a power system to maintain continuous service in the face of rapid and large swings in supply or demand. Traditionally, flexibility is provided in power systems almost entirely by controlling the supply side. In systems with increasing shares of VRES, additional flexibility is needed to maintain system reliability as the variations in supply and demand grow to higher levels. Variable Renewable Energy Sources reduce the flexibility resources in the system by displacing traditional supply side flexibility providers while simultaneously increasing the need for flexibility due to their inherent intermittent nature. This creates a “flexibility gap” that will need to be covered by new flexibility options [2].

The most significant source of flexibility in a scenario with high penetration of Variable Renewable Energy Sources is demand response (DR). DR provides an opportunity for consumers to play a significant role in the operation of the electric grid by reducing or shifting their electricity usage in response to time-based rates or other forms of financial incentives. DR programs are being used by some electric system planners and operators, using mainly the flexibility provided by industrial buildings connected to high-voltage (HV) grid, as a resource option for balancing supply and demand. The new challenge is to unlock the very high potential of DR in the distribution grid [3] where the main sources of flexibility are the residential and tertiary buildings, representing 70% of the total DR potential [4]. Enabling DR potential of residential and tertiary buildings will result in a more active role of the distribution system operator (DSO) and will pave the way to new services at local level.

1.2 THE DRiVE PROJECT

DRiVE is a research and innovation action funded by the European Commission. It aims at unlocking the Demand-Response potential of residential and tertiary buildings in the distribution grid through a full-fledged platform bridging seamlessly the value-chain from planning and design of assets/buildings towards optimal operations in the next generation smart grids, paving the way to a fully deployed Demand-Response market in the distribution network.

To focus efforts, a set of objectives have been established, namely:

1. Unlock Demand-Response potential in residential and tertiary buildings through universally interoperable solutions which integrate innovative forecasting and optimisation algorithms.
2. Optimise distribution grid flexibility through a multi-agent based Demand-Response Information and Communication Technology platform for aggregators which adopts last advances in distributed real-time control and artificial intelligence.
3. Develop cyber-security services for smart grids.
4. Develop innovative business models for participation in Demand-Response schemes in the distribution grid.
5. Create a customer portal engaging end-users in Demand-Response schemes.
6. Demonstration of the project in multiple pilots involving real district data and grid stakeholders.

1.3 THE PRESENT DOCUMENT

This document intends to analyse the context of application of the DRIVe project, thus providing a comprehensive overview of the field in order to serve both as a compilation of the base knowledge of the consortium and to support elicitation of requirements for the solution to be developed during the project.

Section 2 covers energy management systems already available for tertiary and residential buildings while section 3 discusses interoperability standards and communication protocols specific to emerging smart grids. Section 4 reviews the state of the art of algorithms for forecasting, control and decentralized optimisation and the research activity intended during the project in these fields. All together, these topics will be the starting point to accomplish objectives 1 and 2 mentioned above. Also, some references to work in demonstration pilots are provided in section 3 (objective 6).

Section 5 discusses the problem of congestion in distribution grids and how Demand-Response is the appropriate approach these days where the penetration of variable renewable energy sources is transforming the traditional grid.

Smart grids entail global connectivity and thus vulnerability to cyber-attacks. Detailed discussion on this topic is given in section 6, which sets the basis for addressing objective 3.

Section 7 covers stakeholders in the Demand-Response ecosystem and section 8 deals with user expectations on the future of the energy market. Both establish the basis for working on the development of new business models for Demand-Response (objective 4).

Section 9 elaborates on user engagement techniques, which will be crucial for the unlocked Demand-Response potential to be actually brought to market by end-users, and sets the foundation for the development of a customer portal within the project (objective 5).

2 ENERGY MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS

In this section, an overview of the current state of development of market solutions across Europe for energy management systems in buildings (both residential and tertiary) is provided.

The term “residential buildings” refers to all kinds of dwellings, including multi-family buildings, whereas “tertiary buildings” refers to facilities intended for commercial or service use, such as office buildings, hotels, shopping malls and sport centres.

For the purpose of this study, the term “energy management system” (EMS) refers to all the software and hardware equipment in charge of supervising and controlling the energy-related assets in the building and it sometimes includes some added value in terms of energy efficiency or cost optimisation. Thus, it includes: controllers, sensors, valves, actuators, variable speed drives and central supervisory software in the building [5].

In the following paragraphs, tertiary buildings and residential buildings will be treated separately to take into account the differentiated historical trajectories and current situations.

2.1 ENERGY MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS IN TERTIARY BUILDINGS

In tertiary buildings, presence of Energy Management Systems goes back to many years. They are also known as BMSs (Building Management Systems) and they enable the supervision and control of one or more technical services from one centralised location in the building. This includes at least heating, ventilation and air conditioning (HVAC) and often lighting (which together account for most of the total energy use). Other technical services in the building -such as fire detection, security system, etc.- usually have their own independent supervisory software, although the trend towards the smart building concept aims at having all these services integrated under a single supervisory software in the building or, even, under a single supervisory software for a multi-building campus or a multi-site building stock (e.g., of a global corporation).

In the following subsections, an overview of the typical components within the scope of Energy Management Systems in tertiary buildings is provided and a pragmatic approach to join the new trend of internet of things (IoT) is introduced. Also, communication protocols commonly used and typical functionalities for asset management are discussed.

2.1.1 Typical architecture

Figure 1 will serve as a guide to review the main technical features of the components in a typical architecture of an Energy Management System. This can be considered as representative of the situation in most of the tertiary buildings.

Figure 1: Typical architecture in a tertiary building Energy Management System

At the bottom of the architecture are the **energy-related assets**. Traditional (energy-consuming) examples of those are: Air Handling Units (AHUs), fan-coils, boilers and chillers for Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning (HVAC) service, or lamps for lighting service. More modern (energy-storing or energy-producing) examples are: geothermal heat pumps, electrical batteries or photovoltaic panels, which may have been integrated under the same Energy Management System in the building. Unfortunately, when new services -such as renewable energy systems or electric vehicle (EV) charging stations- are implemented after the general construction and commissioning of the building has been completed, chances are very high that these services have their own particular Energy Management System.

The following level in the architecture are **control devices**, such as sensors, actuators, variable speed drives (VSDs) or Direct Current/Alternating Current inverters. These devices directly govern the energy-related assets by obeying commands coming from controllers in the form of discrete (analog or digital) signals or by means of field buses (serial communication links).

One level up are the **controllers**, which are responsible for running automation logic (start and stop sequences, interlocks, etc.) and regulation loops (Proportional-Integrative or Proportional-Integrative-Derivative) to maintain certain variables stable, such as temperatures. Controllers communicate with each other through a **control network** to share information and to collaborate to give the whole service (e.g., Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning) a coherent behaviour.

Finally, at the top of the architecture, there is a central computer which runs the **supervisory software**. This software provides the person responsible for the operation of the building with a graphical user interface (GUI), by means of which adjustments can be made. These adjustments are communicated through the control network to the controllers, which then take care of acting accordingly.

Typically, this central computer is a PC with a Windows OS on top of which a software license for the Energy Management System GUI must be added (Supervisory control and data acquisition (SCADA)) and a development tailored for the building must be done according to the requirements of the building owner.

A lower cost alternative to this tailored approach is lately available from some vendors, which consists in using as central computer a dedicated hardware unit without display and without need for extra software licenses or time-consuming Graphical User Interface development. Instead, it provides a web server functionality with a simplistic, not tailorable GUI, which is available through the Local Area Network (LAN) from any web browser.

According to [5], there are essentially two groups of EMS manufacturers. The first includes the major multinational companies Honeywell [6], Johnson Controls [7], Schneider Electric [8], Siemens [9] and UTC [10]. All of them are present in most countries of the developed world and, together, they account for 70% of market share. The second group of vendors are much smaller and have less geographical coverage. Some examples of those with presence in Europe are Delta Controls [11], Priva [12], Sauter [13] and Trane [14].

2.1.2 New trends: the internet of things

The concept of internet of things (IoT) envisions a future in which individual objects -such as home appliances, vehicles, pieces of industrial equipment, etc.- are embedded with sensors, actuators, computing capability and network connectivity. Each of these objects will be able to interact with other objects through the Internet and behave in ways that will bring new added value not possible before. More specifically, Energy Management Systems operating locally at different buildings without interacting with each other cannot reach the same level of performance that will be possible if some IoT infrastructure allows interaction between different agents such as: weather forecasting services, building assets, grid assets and grid operation stakeholders. Indeed, in the latter case, new possibilities for optimisation and flexibility trading are enabled. Smart Grids and Demand-Response solutions can be considered as an application of Internet of Things to the energy system as a whole (generation, transmission, distribution and use).

However, energy-related assets present in the stock of tertiary buildings and even at the latest vendor catalogues are not currently prepared for this vision in which every single device is connected to the Cloud. In the meantime, a workaround for this situation is to apply the *gateway approach*, which includes the following principles:

- Leverage all the existing installations in the building, thus considering the existing Energy Management System (EMS) as a means by which energy-related assets can be governed.
- Install a gateway able to communicate downstream with the EMS and upstream with the Cloud. In case of existing more than one partial, independent EMS (e.g., Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning and PhotoVoltaic) the gateway can bring the opportunity to connect all of them to the Cloud and enable some coordinated behaviour not possible before.
- Implement in the Cloud the IoT functionality which adds value to the stand-alone building. This could be called the software-as-a-service (*SaaS*) EMS, which adds an upper layer of intelligence to the existing EMS in the building. The development of such an additional layer providing Demand-Response capabilities for buildings is within the scope of the DRIVe project.

Figure 2: The gateway approach to Internet of Things

Figure 2 illustrates this approach. Below the gateway, we find typical communication protocols from the building automation industry whereas above the gateway, information technology (IT) industry communications protocols are used (such as TCP/IP, HTTP, AMQP, etc.).

The variety of protocols in the building automation industry entails a certain barrier for the feasibility of the gateway approach in the stock of existing tertiary buildings. To address this issue, the IoT gateway used should support as many protocols as possible in the downward interface (see Figure 2). However, development costs to achieve this goal are significant. The overview in the following paragraphs intends to assist in the strategic selection of those protocols that can maximise interoperability of the IoT gateway while keeping reasonable development effort.

The communication protocol used in the control network of a certain Energy Management System is one of its essential, defining features and it conditions its capability to interoperate with third-party vendor equipment. The major protocols that are now mainly used in Energy Management System control networks are BACnet [15], LonWorks [16] and KNX [17]. These are open (i.e., multi-vendor) protocols specifically developed for the building industry.

Other protocols are also used in tertiary buildings but with more specific scopes:

- Modbus [18] (very common in devices such as meters, Variable Speed Drive (VSD), smart chillers, etc.);
- Digital Addressable Lighting Interface (DALI) [19] (specific for smart lighting devices);
- Open Platform Communication (OPC) [20] (commonly used as a way to open access to the EMS supervisory software from third party software).

A third group of protocols consists in proprietary protocols developed for air conditioning equipment - basically variable refrigerant volume (VRV) technology- by vendors such as Mitsubishi, Daikin, Panasonic, LG, Samsung and Hitachi.

The need for interoperability between different subsystems in a building, which use the variety of protocols above mentioned, has led to the existence of vendors specialized in inter-protocol gateways to meet these needs. Some examples are: INTESIS [21], ANYBUS [22], TRIDIUM [23].

Moreover, a fourth group of protocols exist which are related to the real Internet of Things and these consist of a myriad of different stacked protocols:

- LoRaWAN [24] for cheap extra sensors,
- Open Charge Point Protocol (OCPP) [25] and Open Charge Point Interface (OCPI) [26] for Electric Vehicle,
- Proprietary cloud/local interface towards static electric batteries etc., e.g. via Ethernet, but Bluetooth/WiFi also already available.

For the purposes of the DRiVE project, it is considered that the IoT gateway should support, at least, communication through OPC, BACnet and Modbus. Indeed, OPC appears as the most natural way in which a third-party software, e.g. located in the IoT gateway, could access the existing Energy Management System supervisory software: OPC allows to modify settings in the supervisory software, just as a human would do by manipulating its Graphical User Interface.

An alternative way to access the existing Energy Management System could be through BACnet, in case that this is the protocol used in the control network. BACnet is widely used in the building automation industry and, unlike other control network protocols, its operative philosophy allows the IoT gateway to govern assets without major conflicts with the EMS supervisory software.

Finally, Modbus is a protocol widely supported by meters and sensors. When a need for additional new devices arises to complete an energy management solution in an existing installation, Modbus is a reasonable choice.

2.1.3 Asset management

Two groups of energy-related assets can be distinguished. The first includes Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning (HVAC) and lighting equipment. This correspond to the traditional technical services aiming at ensuring comfort in the building and, thus, are energy-consuming assets.

Typically, Energy Management Systems implement basic automation functionalities for these assets which can be adjusted from the central supervisory software, namely: definition of on/off schedules, instant on/off commands and regulation of indoor temperature based on Proportional-Integrative or Proportional-Integrative-Derivative techniques. Also, other more efficiency-oriented functionalities are sometimes included: free-cooling and night-cooling for HVAC and automatic regulation of artificial lighting to leverage natural lighting.

Load shedding is also a feature commonly implemented for not critical Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning and lighting in case of main power supply outage. However, this feature usually has been intended and engineered to reduce sizing of alternative power supplies (e.g., diesel generator set) and not to react to a request external to the building. Therefore, it is not directly available for use within DR schemes.

In general, with a view at enabling this first group of assets for DR schemes, it appears as a more advantageous strategy to rely on the more basic functionalities of the building Energy Management System (instant on/off commands and regulation set-points) and govern them from a cloud-based solution (Software-as-a-service EMS) through the IoT gateway.

The second group of assets are energy-producing or energy-storing, namely: micro-wind turbines, photovoltaic (PV) panels, geothermal heat pumps, electrical batteries, Electric Vehicle charging stations, etc. Here the building Energy Management System intends to optimally manage energy flows and decides whether the locally generated energy goes directly to auto-consumption (thus saving consumption from the grid) or it goes to local storage or even is injected into the grid.

This kind of optimisation can be considered as a participation on implicit Demand-Response schemes based on fix tariffs. However, participation in implicit Demand-Response based on real-time prices and in explicit Demand-Response requires the connection of the building to the cloud and, thus, is not currently provided by existing building Energy Management Systems. Again, the strategy for turning these assets into fully DR-enabled would be to connect them to a cloud-based solution either directly, if they support this possibility, or by means of a IoT gateway.

To allow the optimal control of various assets, the typical Energy Management Systems do not contain enough sensors and therefore additions are needed (e.g. extra temperature, flows, electrical sub- meters, CO₂, occupancy, etc.). Since Moore's law helps high speed innovations on this type of sensors, the typical Energy Management Systems cannot follow these fast advancements and hence additions of new sensors typically lie in the fourth category of communication protocols as referred to in section 2.1.2.

2.1.4 Conclusions

Energy Management Systems in tertiary buildings encompass a significant number of components organized in a multi-layer architecture (see Figure 1). The software embodying the logic of control of the energy-related assets is distributed across different hardware units (controllers and central computer) and it has been engineered and integrated in a tailored fashion (turn-key project). As a result, in the context of the stock of existing buildings, upgrading such an architecture with additional functionalities such as energy efficiency or cost optimisation can be technically challenging or practically unadvisable. Total refurbishment of the existing Energy Management System is also a hardly justifiable alternative unless other factors like obsolescence are present.

In this scenario, trying to respect existing infrastructure and using it as a means by which to govern energy-related assets seems the most reasonable option. In this sense, a gateway approach to the IoT (see Figure 2) opens the possibility to add an upper layer of intelligence (SaaS EMS) on top of the local building EMS. The keys for the success of this approach include: (a) enough interoperability of the IoT gateway with the variety of communication protocols that can be found in the building automation industry and (b) accessing the most basic functionalities in the EMS to gain remote governance of energy-related assets in a simple, predictable fashion.

2.2 ENERGY MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS IN RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS

2.2.1 Energy consumption

The built environment accounts for roughly 40% of all energy consumption and it is responsible for 36% of the greenhouse gas emissions in Europe. Residential buildings account for around half of this where this energy load is primarily driven by demand for Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning, domestic hot water, lighting and appliance loads. In many places in Europe, because of climate conditions, heating and hot water production dominate the annual residential energy consumption [27].

2.2.2 Influence of occupant behaviour

Recent studies have highlighted the importance of occupant behaviour in the end energy consumption of buildings [28]. Nowhere this trend is more obvious than in modern, very high efficiency buildings where a "human gap" in performance means that buildings consistently under-perform compared to their theoretical performance [29], [30]. Given stringent building code requirements introduced as a result of the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD), this is concerning information.

This realisation has led to drastic changes in energy management systems in residential buildings. From classic rule-based control systems [31] to model predictive controllers [32] and agent-based technologies [33], [34], buildings are now in the third wave of Energy Management Systems. Recent advances in artificial intelligence and more specifically machine learning have created a new hype cycle around possible applications to smart homes. Amongst the most popular of these lies in creating a connected intelligence that can, over time, learn the building occupants' behaviour and moods [35]. By tighter integration with voice activated systems and assistive robots, this has the potential to revolutionise modern living spaces, by improving on current comfort levels while simultaneously reducing the energy needs [36], [37].

2.2.3 The role of Energy Management Systems

At the heart of any such evolution is a central Energy Management System. A modern Energy Management System takes on multiple tasks in the daily operation of a building, namely:

1. Collection of sensor data;
2. Data processing and analysis;
3. Derive a policy to optimise towards a set objective;
4. Execute the policy by instructing controllable devices.

The most obvious objective for an Energy Management System is to optimise for energy efficiency [38], [39]. This means reducing the total energy consumption in the building by making it more responsive to occupant behaviour (and continuing to respect comfort bounds set by the user). Examples of such optimisation include occupancy based heating or lighting [38]. This has spawned a vast smart thermostat market, which offers different variants.

However, an Energy Management System can go far beyond simple occupancy based control. By integrating an Energy Management System with energy markets, price-based optimisation can be carried out to reduce the overall bill for the household [40]. This is already possible with dual-pricing mechanisms which incentivise consumption during off-peak hours. Additionally, the EMS can prioritise local consumption of renewable energy from e.g. solar PhotoVoltaic panels [41], [42]. Likewise, aggregations of many residential buildings can be used to provide ancillary services to the grid in the form of congestion management and frequency response (typically using fast responding batteries or Electric Vehicles) [43], [44]. This requires many Energy Management Systems to come together and coordinate their control actions.

2.2.4 Current situation

At the heart of any Energy Management System, lie smart algorithms which can perform better energy management than existing alternatives. These alternatives include, most commonly, traditional rule-based control systems which dominate residential Energy Management System. A rule-based controller usually takes the form of a series of if-then conditions which dictate how different devices in the residential building should respond to occupant behaviour or environmental disturbances [31]. This is problematic because it means that a rule-base controller cannot adapt dynamically to changing occupant preferences and is demonstrably sub-optimal both for maintaining occupant comfort and optimizing energy efficiency (or any other objective) [45].

Another well-established alternative is model predictive control (MPC) [32], however this usually presupposes the existence of a “dynamics model” which is then optimised for a predefined objective as mentioned above. This model can take on many forms; it can for example be a thermal model of the building or the hot water vessel, or a transport model to estimate air quality for the ventilation system, etc. Traditional Model Predictive Controls, while widely applied in commercial settings, are less attractive in residential buildings because they require the existence of models requiring human domain expertise. This is an expensive and time-consuming proposition which cannot be undertaken for every single new residential building [46].

Data-driven modelling and optimisation circumvents this dependence on a human domain expert. This means that no prior model is required and learning is carried out online using sensor data, thereby improving the generalisation potential. However, this solution has also bred an increasing dependence on sensor data. While plummeting costs and the upsurge in interest in the Internet of Things has definitely aided in alleviating this, additional sensing does increase costs, both from investment and operational perspectives. This reduces the attractiveness from a cost perspective.

Through innovative research, this sensor dependence can be minimised. An example of this is research into exploring the trade-off between additional sensing and agency (i.e. a single agent system vs. a multi-agent system). It has been demonstrated that additional sensing is largely synonymous with the effect of multiple agents, under certain conditions [47]. This reduces the investment and operational maintenance costs, and makes the value proposition of the energy management system more attractive.

2.2.5 Challenges and future opportunities

These advances have, and will be, enabled by the rise of Internet of Things [48], [49]. Nowadays, smartphones, wearable devices and connected sensors allow service providers to gather and process data at unprecedented scales. However, even in the presence of ubiquitous sensors, the gathered data is often insufficient to perform all required tasks of inference and reasoning [37]. Additional challenges remain as well, the transition from passive monitoring to active control requires a substantial effort in both developing artificial intelligence systems and creating the platforms required to translate software commands into hardware actions. Furthermore, all of this needs considerable storage, bandwidth and processing power resources for transferring the generated data to a central server and processing it.

The alternative of distributed computation [50], while theoretically attractive, requires stringent hardware constraints placed at the end users premises possibly driving costs higher. Large scale collection and storage of occupant data also creates data privacy and security concerns [51], either through design negligence or malicious attacks by hackers. Most recently, reinforcement learning algorithms – a form of artificial intelligence - have been demonstrated to optimise operational characteristics of buildings towards a number of objectives [42], [47]. One advantage of such data driven systems is their ability to learn over time, which enables distributed deployment and can be more computationally efficient than traditional model predictive approaches (as the agent can learn optimal policies instead of optimizing at every time instant).

3 INTEROPERABILITY STANDARDS AND COMMUNICATION PROTOCOLS BETWEEN FLEXIBLE RESOURCES AND THE GRID

Any demand response mechanism implies the existence of a flexible resource, that can be controlled by an external control signal.

Flexible resources in the context of DRiVE are for example:

- An office building (COMSA pilot), controlled by a local Energy Management System;
- An energy storage system (ADO pilot);
- A wind turbine (Giesenwind pilot);
- A heat pump (DEVO pilot).

If we want our control to be based on input vectors from the electrical grid, as is the main objective of DRiVE, we need to establish an end-to-end chain of communication between the flexible element, our control mechanism (SaaS EMS), and finally the stakeholders of the electricity market.

This topic cannot be reduced to a single protocol or interoperability standard. It will rather take an entire chain of protocols, each governed by its own standard, in order to establish this end-to-end interoperability.

This section aims to describe some of the possible choices regarding these end-to-end communication chains and the standards by which the elements in the chain are governed.

It should be the objective of the different DRiVE work packages to further refine these choices, based on input from the ongoing research and the circumstances of the pilots.

3.1 ABOUT EUROPEAN STANDARDISATION¹

In Europe, standards are developed and agreed by the three officially recognised European Standardisation Organisations: the European Committee for Standardisation (CEN) [52], the European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardisation (CENELEC) [53] and the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) [54].

CEN, CENELEC and their national members and committees work jointly to develop and define standards that are considered necessary by market actors and/or to support the implementation of European legislation.

A majority of European Standards are initiated by business and developed in partnership with other stakeholders. Around 30% are mandated by the European Commission in the framework of EU legislation.

The European Standardisation System is unique in the world. After the publication of a European Standard, each national standards body or committee is obliged to withdraw any national standard in conflict with the new European Standard. Hence, one European Standard becomes the national standard in all the 34-member countries of CEN and/or CENELEC.

¹ Summarised from the mission statements of CEN and CENELEC and the charter of the Smart Grid workgroup
Deliverable D2.1 23 Version 1.0
Requirements: Context of Application 7 February 2018
This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under Grant Agreement n°774431.

CEN and CENELEC have defined a dedicated “sector of standardisation”² around energy management. It is centred around 5 topics: energy labelling, eco design, energy management, smart grids and smart meters. The workgroups under smart grids and smart meters are the most relevant for the DRiVE project as they cover the architecture and standards related to demand response mechanisms. As demand response is the main objective of DRiVE it is clear that we need to watch this.

The aim of the workgroup energy management is more about improving the energy efficiency of organisations, installations and systems, which is not a direct objective of DRiVE. To date, there are no publications under this branch dealing with demand response mechanisms at all, hence the focus on the workgroup “energy management” can be much less.

At the end of 2014, the CEN-CENELEC-ETSI Smart Grid Coordination Group finalised the following EU mandated reports:

- [Extended Set of Standards support Smart Grids deployment](#) [55]
- [Overview Methodology](#) [56] and its annexes: [General Market Model Development](#) [57], [Smart Grid Architecture Model User Manual](#) [58] and [Flexibility Management](#) [59]
- [Smart Grid Interoperability](#) [60] and its [tool](#) [61]
- [Smart Grid Information Security](#) [62]

Of particular interest is the Smart Grid Architecture Model (SGAM) and its related interoperability standards and, of course, security, which is always important, but also a specific topic for research of the DRiVE project. Both of them are the focus of the next section.

3.2 SMART GRID ARCHITECTURE MODEL & INTEROPERABILITY

The Smart Grid Architecture Model SGAM defines a referenced architecture and also a certain vocabulary. Within the DRiVE project we should take care to use the same terminology whenever possible. Figure 3 depicts the smart grid plane as defined in [58].

² <https://www.cencenelec.eu/standards/Sectors/SustainableEnergy/Management/Pages/default.aspx>

Figure 3: Smart Grid Architecture Model (SGAM). Source: [58]

There are many interoperability protocols and standards for smart grid but CEN-CENELEC-ETSI also provides a tool under the form of an excel file to allow a quick selection to the standards which may apply. The link to this tool can be found in [61].

Note that there is an abundance of standards and that this table (dating from 2014) does not even reflect all of them and certainly not the innovative ones which do not have the EU standard status yet. In DRiVE, for the sake of time, we would need to make a sub-selection based on pragmatic considerations.

We propose to use the following criteria:

- Consider the standards for Distributed Energy Resources (DER) only;
- Use the “state of the art” knowledge as existing with the DRiVE partners;
- Consider the real field situation of each pilot and choose the most pragmatic.

The sections 3.3 to 3.5 elaborate upon those selection criteria.

3.3 STANDARDS FOR DISTRIBUTED ENERGY RESOURCES

The DRiVE project main innovation focus is clearly on the domain of Distributed Energy Resources, and its links to the distribution network and the customer premises.

In principle, the objective of DRiVE is not proposing new standards or protocols in the domains of transmission and generation but rather reuse the existing ones as they are applicable for the pilots. In terms of interoperability DRiVE needs to cover all layers, but it is not expected to change any lower level protocols to equipment on customer premises, possibly with the exception for the fast interactions as this is a specific field of research.

In Table 1 we made the selection for Distributed Energy Resource interoperability protocols and deleted those standards obviously not applicable.

Standardisation organisation	Standards	Title
CEN / CENELEC	EN 61400-25-1,2,3,4	Wind turbines - Part 25-1,2,3,4: Communications for monitoring and control of wind power plants
CEN / CENELEC	EN 50438	Requirements for the connection of micro-generators in parallel with public low-voltage distribution networks
CEN / CENELEC	CLC prTS 50549-3	Conformance testing for connection of Distributed Energy Resource systems to Low-Voltage and Medium-Voltage network
IEC	IEC 61784-1	Industrial communication networks - Profiles - Part 1: Fieldbus profiles
CEN / CENELEC	EN 61724	Photovoltaic system performance monitoring - Guidelines for measurement, data exchange and analysis
IEC	IEC 61850-80-4	Mapping of COSEM metering model over IEC 61850
IEC	IEC 61850-8-2	Communication networks and systems for power utility automation - Part 8-2: Specific communication service mapping (SCSM) - Mappings to web-services
IEC	IEC 61850-90-10	Object Models for Scheduling
IEC	IEC 61850-90-11	Communication networks and systems for power utility automation - Part 90-11: Methodologies for modelling of logics for IEC 61850 based applications
IEC	IEC 61850-90-12	Communication networks and systems for power utility automation - Part 90-11: Use of IEC 61850 over WAN
IEC	IEC 61850-90-15	Hierarchical DER system model
IEC	IEC 61850-90-2	Use of IEC 61850 for the communication between substations and control centres
IEC	IEC 61850-90-7	Communication networks and systems for power utility automation - Part 90-7: IEC 61850 object models for photovoltaic, storage, and other DER inverters
IEC	IEC 61850-90-9	Object Models for Batteries
CEN / CENELEC	EN 62325 (all parts)	Framework for energy market communications
IEC	IEC 62351	Power systems management and associated information exchange - Data and communications security

IEC	IEC 62361-102	CIM-IEC 61850 Harmonisation
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Table 1: Distributed Energy Resource interoperability protocols with possible implications for DRiVE

We propose to use this table as starting point of reference, since the DRiVE project should adhere to existing standards when possible or use them to guide base research upon. The DRiVE project however should not be restricted by the existing standards as it is an explicit objective of a research project to create new knowledge. This knowledge should be used to influence the EU standardisation efforts.

It is not necessary at this point in time, to discuss these standards in detail. Depending on the architectural choices we need to make in WP2, WP4 and the pilots, many of these standards will turn out to be irrelevant for the DRiVE project.

As an example, we can take EN 64100 “Communications for monitoring and control of wind power plants”. This standard will either be relevant or not depending on how, and if, the owners of the wind turbine in Giessenwind pilot will allow us to directly steer their assets. It is far more likely that they will provide us with a simple interface connection to their own management system. We will need to explore this based on field survey in the said pilot.

In Table 1, we chose to document all standards which could possibly be relevant. But the pragmatic approach will be that in the course of the DRiVE project we will narrow these choices further down and then study the impact caused by relevant standards. This impact will need to be documented in the deliverables of the relevant work packages.

3.4 KNOWLEDGE OF THE PARTNERS REGARDING (EMERGING) STANDARDS

In addition to existing EU standards, we should surely also look at the following emerging standards:

Universal Smart Energy Framework (USEF) [63]: is an emerging standard, not yet published by CEN/CENELEC, which is mainly applied in the Netherlands for communication between an aggregator (AGR) and the electricity market. It is a protocol but also a market model which defines the interaction between the main players: AGRs, prosumers, distribution service operators (DSOs), balance responsible parties (BRPs) and transmission system operators (TSOs). It has been piloted by Enervalis in the course of the RENnovates EU-680603 project [64], between Enervalis and two dominant DSO’s in the Dutch market, Alliander and Stedin. A full description of USEF and even a reference application can be found at the USEF website [63]. As described in the DRiVE grant agreement, USEF will be the basis for interoperability of the DRiVE solution with the electricity market. It might be needed to extend upon USEF based on the research for fast response or multiple client systems.

Open Automated Demand Response (OpenADR) [65]: is an American standard for interoperability between electrical devices, energy management systems and the grid. It is very relevant for the DRiVE project because it explicitly addresses the topic of demand response of Distributed Energy Resources towards the grid.

In more detail, according to their website [65]:

The mission of the OpenADR Alliance is to foster the development, adoption, and compliance of the Open Automated Demand Response (OpenADR) standards through collaboration, education, training, testing and certification.

The OpenADR Alliance formed in 2010, from industry stakeholders, to build on the foundation of technical activities to support the development, testing, and deployment of commercial OpenADR and to facilitate its acceleration and widespread adoption. This approach needs to engage service providers (such as electric utilities and systems operators) within the domain of the Smart Grid that publish OpenADR signals, as well as the facilities or third-party entities that consume them to manage electric loads. The OpenADR Alliance will enable all stakeholders to participate in automated Demand-Response, dynamic pricing, and electricity grid reliability.

Unfortunately, to date, none of the European Distribution System Operator or Transmission System Operator is actually using OpenADR and there is hardly any equipment on the European market, which is controllable via OpenADR.

Due to these circumstances, it is highly unlikely that the pilots will be able to use OpenADR in real live circumstances. However, evolutions of OpenADR standards and the market adoption of OpenADR in Europe should be followed up by the DRiVE market watch.

In any case, OpenADR can/should be a useful source for inspiration in DRiVE research topics.

Recently there have been press releases by the OpenADR [65] organisation, indicating contacts, between Universal Smart Energy Framework (USEF) and OpenADR [65] to join forces for standardisation of flexibility programs. When this evolution sets through the likelihood of this effort in becoming the dominant standard on the market would be high. DRiVE should watch this evolution closely.

EEbus [66]: is an open standard originated in Germany but it is in the meantime endorsed by many European Companies including building companies, manufacturers of building management systems, HVAC, battery and car manufactures. It does not explicitly focus on Demand-Response mechanisms, but it is rather a universal framework for formulating use cases for interfacing with energy consuming or producing equipment. Like OpenADR there is not much equipment on the market supporting EEbus yet, but it is surely to be watched closely and to be used as a source of guideline.

It has been piloted however for a first time by Enervalis on some devices (solar inverter, E-meter, battery) in the course of the RENnovates EU-680603 project [64]. Information can be found at [66].

3.5 INTEROPERABILITY PROTOCOLS AS DEFINED BY THE PILOTS

In the DRiVE project, 5 pilots are defined:

- Blaenau Gwent in Wales;
- DEVO in Venendaal in the Netherlands;
- Giesenwind Wind wind farm in the Netherlands;
- ADO Stadium in Den Haag;
- COMSA Head office.

In order to avoid excessive effort for tasks which are not really producing new know-how, it is the intent to integrate these pilots into the basic architecture as existing at Enervalis.

Figure 4 depicts a high-level architecture scheme for data collection and control as it is operational now for residential projects at Enervalis, but just as valid for tertiary buildings and industrial equipment.

In the course of DRiVE, the Enervalis gateway will need to be extended for multi-agent system (MAS) and real time Demand-Response mechanisms, and as such, becomes the local energy gateway (LEG) as described in the Grant Agreement.

Figure 4: Basic architecture for residential projects at Enervalis

Interfaces between the Local Energy Gateway and the customer site equipment:

In WP6 of the DRiVe project, which has as a main task the integration of the pilots, field surveys will need to be done for each of the pilots in order to define the equipment with which we need to interface. The possibilities of the equipment on site will mostly define the interoperability protocol from the equipment towards the Local Energy Gateway. Unless the DRiVe research objectives will force us to introduce/invent a new protocol, we will just reuse existing interfaces and supported lower-level protocols to address the field situation. The changes needed in order to integrate field equipment and to reach the DRiVe research objectives will most probably be limited to the data model and the use cases. For practical purposes, this should be our working assumption when starting WP2 and WP4. Typical interfaces are: Modbus, BACnet, Profibus and LonWorks.

Interfaces between the Local Energy Gateway and the Software-as-a-service (SaaS) Energy Management System

Currently Enervalis uses a heavily encrypted proprietary protocol between the Software-as-a-service (SaaS) EMS and the gateway, running on top of Advanced Message Queuing Protocol (AMQP) [67]. This is done because, to date, there is just no existing standard capable of performing all the tasks as needed (energy management, configuration management, asset management, software update services, remote maintenance, etc.). Should a new standard emerge capable of fulfilling the job, it could be considered during the runtime of the project to, fully or partially, switch over to this emerging standard. Changes to this interface will surely be needed during DRiVe, at least to the data models and Application Programming Interfaces, possibly to the protocol itself for fast response purposes (to be defined in WP2 and WP4).

Interfaces between the SaaS EMS and the Energy market

The protocols towards the electricity market will be defined by the Distribution System Operator in the local network and/or the Transmission System Operator. We will need to work with the situation in the country as it is. Those companies, when not included as a partner in the EU research project itself, are highly unlikely to chance their interfaces just for the sake of a research project. It is up to DRIVe to creatively use what is there already and, if applicable, push recommendations for change in the relevant standardisation committees.

- **Situation in the Netherlands** (pilots DEVO, ADO, Giesenwind)

Enervalis has already implemented a Universal Smart Energy Framework (USEF) standard interface with two Distribution System Operators, Alliander and Stedin, which is already operational. This protocol can be reused in DRIVe for the daily scheduling.

Scholt has an operational interface with the Dutch Transmission System Operator Tennet (running over a proprietary communication system and providing Frequency Containment Reserve (FCR) services with a large static battery of 1MW/1MWh). Enervalis has recently completed the new Tennet interface for Frequency Containment Reserve (FCR) services and this is the interface Scholt will use as of now and also this will be used for the DRIVe project as part of the overall flexibility management. However here advancements beyond the State-of-the-Art will need to be agreed and implemented between Enervalis/Tennet because we will need shorter slotted service allocation which was envisioned by Universal Smart Energy Framework (USEF) but not yet adhered to from the Transmission System Operator.

For the fast response mechanisms, changes or extensions might be needed to both interfaces, also to be determined in WP2.

- **Situation in Spain** (Comsa headquarters pilot)

In Spain, the Transmission System Operator for the whole country is *Red Eléctrica de España*. There are a number of Distribution System Operators but the major ones are: Endesa (to which Comsa headquarters are connected), Iberdrola, Gas Natural Fenosa and E.ON. Neither *Red Eléctrica de España* nor Endesa are involved in the DRIVe project. Therefore, it seems clear that there is no possibility to use their interfaces. Although real, physical tests will be conducted in Comsa headquarters within the project, a simulation of communication between the building and a “fake” DSO and/or TSO might be necessary in order to contribute to the validation of the DRIVe solution.

- **Situation in the UK** (Blaenau Gwent pilot)

The Energy Market in the UK is governed by OFGEM. BGCBC will have to fully comply with OFGEM’s regulations. We have approached the Distribution Network Operator (DNO) for collaboration within the DRIVe project. The Distribution Network Operator (in this case Western Power Distribution) has expressed a willingness to participate at BGCBC’s request in this project. Energy is procured within BGCBC through the National Procurement Service (NPS) framework of procurement. This means that energy costs do not fluctuate within an annual period, for example, between April 2017 to April 2018 energy prices are held at a set rate. Within the UK, energy is predominantly procured on a demand led bases where the consumer only pays for what is used.

3.6 STANDARDS FOR INFORMATION SECURITY AND PRIVACY

In section 3.1, it was highlighted that the EU has set rules and standards for information security on smart grids. These rules and standards are called Smart Grid Information Security (SGIS) and they can be found in the SG-CG/M490/H_ Smart Grid Information Security report as published by the CEN-CENELEC-ETSI Smart Grid Coordination Group in December 2014 [62].

They are mapped according to the Smart grid architecture model (SGAM) architecture model on use cases relevant for smart grid in general, including demand response. It should be a task in WP5 and WP9 to check if any of the DRiVE use cases would conflict with the relevant security and privacy standards.

GDPR: General Data Protection Regulation

At the time of the Smart Grid Information Security report [62], as mentioned above, the text of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [68] protecting the privacy of personal data in the EU was not published yet. The adoption of the regulations by EU member states came in April 17th 2016, the subsequent publication in May 2016. It will become in full force in May 2018, two years after the publication.

As we could be dealing with personal data in some of the DRiVE pilots, we would surely need to be compliant with the General Data Protection Regulation; this should be followed in WP9 (ethics) and WP5 (security).

Originally, it was the intent that the General Data Protection Regulation would replace any local guideline regarding the privacy of personal data. Unfortunately, this was not approved by the EU parliament which makes it so that local regulations in the EU could still be adopted if they are more restrictive. This means that for any pilot, it should be investigated if we are dealing with personal data and which local regulations regarding privacy and security are applicable.

For the Netherlands, the relevant organism is the *Autoriteit Persoonsgegevens* [69] which publishes the regulations on their website. Enervalis and Scholt are already compliant with these regulations for their other project with Dutch customers.

For Spain, the adaption of the EU regulation protecting the privacy of personal data is transposed into the national law called *Ley Organica de Protección de Datos* [70]. As well, there is an official organism, *Agencia Española de Protección de Datos* [71], which is responsible for managing all the legal issues and operational rights concerning privacy data. COMSA Corporacion accomplishes with the above-mentioned regulation and authorises, explicitly, energy data usage coming from its pilot building for DRiVE purposes.

For the UK, data protection is governed by the Data Protection Act 1998. BGCBC are required by UK law to be fully compliant with these regulations.

4 ALGORITHMS AND OPTIMISATION STRATEGIES CURRENTLY IMPLEMENTED FOR BUILDING AND DISTRICT MANAGEMENT

4.1 INTRODUCTION

DRiVE relies on integrating building energy management system (BEMS), multi-agent system (MAS) optimisation, model predictive control (MPC) and computational intelligence (CI) based forecasting to unlock the demand response potential. Existing Computational Intelligence-based forecasting algorithms will be extended by coupling advanced clustering techniques (for profile segmentation) and physics based simulation (for thermal MPC) to improve: (a) granularity and accuracy of prediction, (b) time steps (to minutes from half hourly), and (c) execution speed for use in near real-time grid management. The DRiVE model predictive control (MPC) will then be based on day-ahead forecasting of load, generation and flexibility—enabling the actuation of controlled device(s) at the most suitable time, thereby maximising Demand-Response potential. Next, the optimisation will be based on external control parameters (DR) and the knowledge of storage capabilities—a step forward from current DR approaches. The following review, therefore, focuses on the technologies relevant to the DRiVE solutions.

4.2 FORECASTING TECHNOLOGIES

Forecasting plays a vital role in energy supply and demand management in buildings, districts and grids. The use of methods to obtain an accurate forecast of energy consumption is essential for efficient scheduling and planning of the generation, distribution and use of energy [72]. The forecasting methods depend on the purpose and the time horizon of the forecast, as follows:

- **Very short-term** forecasting time horizon ranges from milliseconds to minutes, and is predominantly used for frequency and voltage control.
- **Short-term** forecasting typically involves the prediction of loads from a few minutes up to a few days ahead, and is predominantly used in load/demand forecasting for operational purposes.
- **Medium-term** forecasting involves horizons from a few days to a few months ahead, and is generally used for electricity price forecasting, risk management and generation planning.
- **Long-term** forecasting has lead times of months, quarters or even years. Their use is predominantly for investment profitability analysis and energy systems planning.

The selection of forecasting methods for implementation depends on the purpose, availability and update of time series data [73], forecasting frequency, and temporal cycle of granularity [74]. Several techniques have been developed over the last few decades to predict future energy demand. Since the DRiVE's goal related to forecasting is pioneering a hybrid building physics and Computational Intelligence-based forecasting solution, this section will review the main forecasting methods which can help to meet this aim.

- **Building physics-based modelling**
Physics-based modelling is a cross-disciplinary field, including elements of applied mathematics, numerical analysis, computational physics, computer graphics, computer vision, and software engineering [75]. Detailed physics-based equations are used in this method to model building components, sub-systems and systems to predict whole buildings and their sub-systems behaviours, such as their energy consumption and indoor environmental conditions [76].

Building physics-based modelling, also known as “engineering method” or “white-box” model, can generally be classified into two categories: (a) the detailed comprehensive and (b) the simplified method.

The **comprehensive method** uses the principles of thermodynamics and heat-balance to calculate the disaggregated energy consumption within a building by considering weather, and building fabric and system information such as building construction and their thermal properties, Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning components and their operation, and may incorporate utility rate schedule as the inputs [77]. The detailed comprehensive physics-based methods of forecasting use building simulation engines such as EnergyPlus, ESP-r, TRANSYS, and e-QUEST. EnergyPlus is deemed as one of the most comprehensive physics-based engine, which is a whole building energy simulation program that is used to model energy use and indoor conditions in buildings [78].

The **simplified method** is a single-measure method, such as the use of the degree-days in energy-use estimations. They are predominantly used for comparing the heating requirements between different locations and for demonstrating compliance with building regulations. The bin or ambient-temperature frequency method performs heating and cooling energy calculations at many different outdoor dry bulb temperature conditions (i.e. bins), and multiplying the results by the number of hours of occurrence of each condition (bin) [79].

- **Computational intelligence technique**

Computational intelligence (CI) methods have been widely employed in forecasting building energy demand, where their results showed efficiency and versatility to deal with temporal variations than other forecasting methods [80, 81]. Computational intelligence -based methods can effectively forecast energy demand with higher accuracy and less input variables [82]. Computational intelligence is a rapidly advancing research field and includes a collection of various computation techniques, including but not limited to: artificial neural network (ANN) and its many hybrid variants, fuzzy logic (FL), and support vector machine (SVM) [83].

Artificial neural networks (ANNs) are flexible computing frameworks for modelling a broad range of nonlinear problems [84]. As a non-linear forecasting method, Artificial Neural Network determines the complex relationship between the inputs and outputs without prior knowledge [85]. This method is typically used to trace previous load patterns for predicting future loads and can adapt to the future changes with new data [86]. It is capable to forecast short-, medium-, and long-term energy consumption [87], and able to consider different variable types from dichotomous to continuous, while offering favourable computation/execution time [88]. Compared with physics-based methods in forecasting HVAC energy demand, Artificial Neural Networks have been demonstrated to have less error with a simpler model, even the simplest ones using temperature as the only input [82]. In cases with large number of variables, the selection of significant features as input to Artificial Neural Network can be challenging. Principal component analysis (PCA) is often used to reduce the dimension of inputs [89]. Another challenge in ANN-based forecasting is the determination of the optimal number of hidden nodes, which becomes especially challenging for large problems.

Genetic algorithm (GA) is a global search technique that is useful for complex optimisation problems due to its robustness for non-linear problems [90]. Genetic Algorithm is, therefore, used to determine the characteristics of hidden layers in an Artificial Neural Network [91, 92, 93]. The ANN-GA hybrid models are found to minimise errors between the observed and estimated values. The application of **fuzzy logic (FL)** needs fewer observations than many of the other forecasting methods, and can use incomplete data to produce the forecasted values [94].

Support vector machine (SVM) is a supervised learning method with applications in classification and regression [95]. Classification allows one to divide a set of data in several categories, whose characteristics are given by the user. The regression method allows one to describe a set of data by a specific equation [96]. Support Vector Machine uses the structural minimisation principle to achieve a global optimum [97]. It is highly effective in solving non-linear problems, therefore is often used to forecast energy consumption with high accuracy [98].

Figure 5 illustrates the classification of Computational Intelligence techniques for Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning applications.

Figure 5: Classification of computational intelligence techniques with respect to their primary area of application. Source: [99]

Since DRiVe seeks to apply the forecasting methods in both a micro (building) and macro (district) contexts, a point to note is that physics-based methods are more convenient for individual buildings than computational algorithms. On the other hand, it is more appropriate to use computational algorithms for district levels as they can be applied by using historical performance data only [100]. However, historical data must have a high level of statistical significance to obtain better accuracy [101].

4.3 MODEL PREDICTIVE CONTROL

One of the significant advantages of using forecasting algorithms is that they can be embedded as explicit models into prediction-based optimal control, such as Model Predictive Control. DRiVe aims to implement an Model Predictive Control algorithm at each control interval to optimise the future behaviour of the constituent systems and components of the building via the building energy management systems. By using predictive approaches, the fluctuations within energy prices, load profiles and input profiles from renewable energy sources can be handled in an effective way [102]. The performance of an MPC-based energy system crucially depends on the accuracy of the load forecasts [103], response/execution time of the Model Predictive Control algorithm, uncertainty that may be acceptable in the domain of application [104] – all of which are indirectly dependent on the availability of the computation power either on the device or in the Cloud. The formulation of an MPC algorithm in building energy management typically includes a multi-objective mathematical programming model that minimises some functions of cost and energy use, as well as the deviation from thermal comfort ranges [105]. Model Predictive Controls are reported to be particularly suited to the performance objective of buildings where thermal comfort needs to be ensured with minimal energy consumption [106]. Figure 6 illustrates a simplified process and data-flow diagram for an Model Predictive Control control framework with DRiVe’s Demand-Response enabling component.

Figure 6: A simplified process and data-flow diagram for Model Prediction Control. DRIVe extends the generic MPC framework by enabling DR signals in the MPC algorithm

The basic idea of Model Predictive Control is to form a model that is able to represent the future behaviour of building cooling/heating dynamics and to provide optimal control actions for a specific time horizon [107]. Different modelling approaches can be employed for implementation of a Model Predictive Control strategy. The first approach is based upon detailed physics-based modelling of cooling and heating dynamics. In this approach, physical characteristics of a building and its Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning components are extracted and fed into a series of energy balance equations. The balance equations are then used for prediction of the future evolution of cooling/heating dynamics [105]. An alternative is to use a data-driven model (e.g. Artificial Neural Networks, Fuzzy logic) to Model Predictive Control by simply fitting a metamodeling to the cooling/heating data regardless of the particular physical structure of the building [108, 109].

4.4 MULTI AGENT SYSTEMS

4.4.1 Introduction

Demand response (DR) is an essential feature of the Smart Grid. The proliferation of distributed energy resources (DER) based on renewable energy sources, batteries, smart appliances and electric vehicles bring new opportunities for DR schemes. This also adds challenges to the energy management task due to increasing the complexity of networks, intermittent nature of Distributed Energy Resources and unpredictable power demand. The optimal energy management strategy is often determined by optimizing the power flow scheduling using centralised or distributed problem-solving approaches.

Multi-agent systems (MAS) have become a prominent tool for the design of the smart grid [110] [111] [112] [113]. Multi-agent systems offer a control paradigm where the system components are represented by intelligent and interacting agents. These agents can exhibit important properties such as autonomy, sociability and proactivity. This paradigm promotes the integration of existing building management system (BMS) and autonomous optimisation components into a holistic architecture that ensures the scalability and parallelisation of algorithms with a limited information exchange. This section reviews the optimisation used for the energy management from a Multi-agent system perspective and outlines a DRIVe strategy.

4.4.2 Centralised optimisation

Centralised optimisation historically has been a primary way to approach the management of electric power systems. In the context of Multi-agent system, it can be viewed as a particular case where different agents communicate with a central agent who performs the computation and determines the energy management strategy while the other agents receive instructions and follow them.

It was shown that a simple optimisation model can determine the optimal timing of appliance operation taking into account both electricity price fluctuations and user preferences [114]. A centralised optimisation was used to reduce the electricity consumption during the peak hours by determining the schedule of consumer's daily tasks according to specified deadlines and the real-time pricing [115]. The energy management problem is often posed in a way to enable the application of efficient traditional optimisation algorithms. In [116], a quadratic optimisation problem was formulated to compute the optimal schedule for a given set of loads while maintaining occupants comfort and PhotoVoltaic generation constraints. Computational intelligence (CI) offers tools that allow to overcome the limitations of traditional optimisation technics. For instance, a genetic algorithm was employed for building energy management to reduce energy demand in peak periods and maximise the use of renewable sources [117].

Although centralised approaches can be effective in providing solutions, their major disadvantage relates to a high communication cost. As in the next generation of electric grids, the number of controllable devices is envisioned to increase, the applicability of centralised approaches will be limited due to the lack of scalability.

4.4.3 Distributed optimisation

Given the structure of electric grids, distributed optimisation is a natural strategy for addressing the above limitation. This also naturally lies into the Multi-agent system paradigm where, in a decentralised way, different agents can communicate, learn consumption trends, perform local optimisations, negotiate energy resources and respond to real-time environmental conditions.

The alternating direction method of multipliers (ADMM) [118] has become a prominent tool for solving distributed optimisation problems due to its suitability for decomposition and convergence guarantees. Alternating direction method of multipliers with a proximal message passing mechanism was used to schedule the power flow and voltage phase angles for devices [119]. A distributed demand response mechanism for operating a microgrid based on ADMM was presented in [120]. ADMM proved effective in the management of local energy communities such as the community of prosumers that coordinate a power consumption to minimise deviations from the target consumption [121] and the aggregated power imbalance [122].

There are various studies that explicitly exploit the Multi-Agent System paradigm for a distributed energy management. In [123], it was demonstrated how a home heating management agent can learn the thermal characteristics of a home and predict local weather conditions in order to provide home owners with real-time information about their daily heating costs. It was also shown how the agent can optimise heating use by minimising the cost and carbon emissions while satisfying the preferences for comfort.

A model of decentralised demand-side management based on Multi-Agent System was developed in [124] where the smart home is considered as a collection of non-deferrable and deferrable loads. The latter are controlled by agents that optimise the deferment of these loads so as to maximise the comfort in the home and minimise energy costs. The study also presented mechanisms for agents to adapt the deferment of their loads instead of just being reactive.

A prototype agent-based platform was presented in [125] to solve the tariff selection problem for homeowners. The platform incorporates algorithms that make predictions for hourly energy usage based on the data provided by smart meters. It also provides recommendations about shifting the power consumption of deferrable loads to off-peak periods thereby maximizing savings. The energy management typically involves the consideration of different conflicting criteria such as costs reduction and comfort.

In [126], a multi-agent comfort and energy system was developed to model alternative management and control of building systems and occupants. In contrast to previous Multi-Agent Systems, this system coordinates both building system devices and building occupants through direct changes to occupant meeting schedules using multi-objective Markov Decision Problems.

4.4.4 Game theory

Game theory studies the interactions between self-interested agents in situations called games. As such, it is a proper analytical framework for Multi-Agent Systems that has a great potential for the application in the Smart Grid. There are non-cooperative game theory and cooperative game theory.

Non-cooperative game theory can be used to analyse a distributed decision making, where agents seek to optimise their own utilities coupled with the actions of the other agents, without coordination or communication. Non-cooperative game theory can be used for distributed demand-side management so as to reduce the peak-to-average ratio [127]. Non-cooperative games can be also applied to devise pricing strategies. When adopting the pricing tariffs that differentiate the energy usage in time and level, the global optimal performance can be achieved at a Nash equilibrium [128]. Non-cooperative game theory is also effective for energy management and Demand-Response applied to multiple smart buildings [129].

In contrast, cooperative game theory considers the agents that are able to communicate and to receive shared utilities. Cooperative games are useful for studying what incentives can be provided for independent agents so that they form a group acting as one entity, as well as a competition between groups of agents. They can be used for devising a cooperative energy exchange mechanism in distribution networks [130].

4.4.5 Reinforcement learning

In Multi-Agent Systems, the agents inhabit an environment whose state changes due to their actions or some external events. The actions of agents can have deterministic or non-deterministic effects. The agents aim at finding the optimal policy that maps states to actions to maximise its expected utility.

Reinforcement learning (RL) is the paradigm where the agent learns, from rewards and punishments, how to interact with an environment to maximise the cumulative reward. Reinforcement learning algorithms exploit two major ideas. The first one is based on sampling to compactly represent the dynamics of the control problem. The second one is to use function approximations to represent value functions [131]. Reinforcement learning for Multi-Agent System is suitable to various scenarios emerging in the smart grid such as demand response in real-life residential buildings [132] and for the trading agent to derive long-term, profit-maximizing policies [133].

4.4.6 DRiVE strategy

DRiVE will address the building and district energy management by a distributed optimisation where the energy network is modelled as a cooperation network that is distributed among different interacting agents. The overall approach will build on the one [134] developed as part of the FP7 MASTERING extending it with new capabilities.

The alternating direction method of multipliers (ADMM) will be adopted as a central tool for optimisation. ADMM iteratively solves a dual problem by minimising the augmented Lagrangian function with respect to primal and dual variables. These variables have a meaningful interpretation within the energy network. The primal variables represent the power required by the network and the dual variables show the price of the energy. Each iteration of ADMM involves three steps that can be executed in parallel between different agents. The first step finds locally the optimal power schedules. The second step computes the power requested by the network. The third step updates scaled dual variables representing the energy price. The convergence criteria are defined locally for primal and dual residuals. When these are satisfied, the algorithm returns a protocol that governs the operation of the energy network in a decentralised and cost-effective way allowing the introduction of a larger amount of renewable energy sources while insuring grid stability.

In DRiVE, the ADMM optimisation algorithm will be extended in order to:

- Participate in a transparent way to multiple Demand-Response schemes;
- Support the management of flexibility for Low-Voltage and Medium-Voltage assets (e.g. virtual power plants, storage, Combined Heat & Power, etc.);
- Provide new ancillary services (such as congestion management and power quality) to Distribution System Operator during the Plan & Validate phase;
- Integrate home heating as an active load through the Model Predictive Control module;
- Interface with the real-time management components that intervene in the operate phase.

Furthermore, the multi-agent algorithmic framework will be coupled with the Blockchain technology (and in particular with the NRG-X-Change framework developed within SmartPowerSuite) that will allow for peer-to-peer payment transactions among participants.

5 CONGESTION MANAGEMENT AND FAST DEMAND RESPONSE IN DISTRIBUTION GRID OPERATIONS

Having in mind the DRiVE solution must be designed to be attractive and beneficial not only to prosumers and the society as a whole, but also to Distribution System Operators, this section is devoted to identifying the current techniques used for distribution grid management (section 5.1.) and the emerging need to introduce Fast Demand-Response (FDR) (section 5.2). As such, this chapter serves the dual purpose of:

- (a) establishing the baseline for benchmarking the usability of the DRiVE platform upgrade of the current state of the art from the point of view of Distribution System Operators, and
- (b) futureproofing the DRiVE solution by identifying the, as of yet non-standardized, Fast Demand-Response requirements which the DRiVE solution should integrate in order to meet the emerging needs of Distribution System Operators and Balance Responsible Parties.

5.1 DISTRIBUTION SYSTEM OPERATOR’S TOOLS FOR CONGESTION MANAGEMENT

This section of the report defines the current tools that Distribution System Operators use for congestion management. In the initial paragraph, the role of the Distribution System Operators in the energy market is explained, with the focus on the physical part of the system. In the next paragraph, the term congestion is explained and why congestion should be managed. Then the focus shifts to the tools Distribution System Operators currently have at their disposal for managing congestion, the changing needs for congestion management and the role that demand response can play to fulfil those needs. The last paragraph provides a summary of the information in this section.

5.1.1 Role of the Distribution System Operator

To analyse the tools of the Distribution System Operator for congestion management, first the role of the Distribution System Operator in the electricity market structure has to be studied. A simplified overview of the electricity market, the market participants and the transactions are shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Overview of transactions within the electricity market. Source: [135]

The overview consists of a physical subsystem and a commodity subsystem. The physical subsystem comprises the production units on distribution level -i.e. the Distributed Generation (DG) operator- and on transmission level -i.e. Large Power Producer (LPP)-, the transmission network (managed by the Transmission System Operator), the distribution network (managed by the DSO) and the loads (consumer).

- (1) The generated electricity by the large power producer is fed to the Transmission System Operator
 - (2) The Transmission System Operator transports the electricity to the Distribution System Operator.
 - (3) The electricity generated by the Distributed Generation operator is directly fed to the Distribution System Operator or in some cases even directly (6) to the consumer.
 - (4) If the Distribution System Operator has a surplus of electricity in its network, it feeds upwards into the transmission grid.
 - (5) If not, the Distribution System Operator delivers the electricity to the consumer
- The commodity subsystem, in contrast with the physical power streams, consists of economic transactions and is merely administrative in nature (7 - 18) [135].

Distribution System Operators are thus responsible for the distribution of energy on the distribution grid. Additionally, they are obliged to do this in the most cost-effective way. Both maintaining the power quality at distribution level and ensuring the security of supply at distribution level are necessary in order to deliver energy to each consumer within its own area of operation. For Distribution System Operators, it is therefore their task to maintain the grid operation, secure the supply, connect and give access to the network, and collect and provide (metering) data to third parties [136].

5.1.2 The need for congestion management

In the liberalised electricity market in the EU both producers and consumers have a free choice in the geographical placement of their facilities. Since the geographical location of production units can differ from the location the grid design accounted for, the electricity grid is not always sufficient to physically transfer the traded electricity from the producer to the consumer. Unlike congestion of traffic for instance, congestion of electricity does not lead to a jam or slower transfer of energy but to the heating up of the transmission lines. Congestion in electricity grids is caused by scheduled flows that would exceed safe and reliable operation margins when actually implemented. Physical congestion should never be allowed to occur, as these would damage the equipment and possibly lead to blackouts [137].

5.1.3 Distribution System Operator's tools for congestion management

In order to avoid situations of congestion, a distribution system operator could ensure to have sufficient grid capacity available to cope with demand at all times. For the congestion management, the Distribution System Operator has three options: reinforcing the grid, curtailment or re-dispatching [138]. Reinforcing the grid via a fit and forget approach is the first option and historically the dominant option for a Distribution System Operator to avoid congestion and voltage problems. In this approach, enough investments in network components (i.e. transformers and cables) are made to always avoid congestion problems. Curtailment and re-dispatch are in this approach regarded as temporary solutions until the grid can be reinforced, where generation or demand curtailment is used in cases of system security related events and re-dispatching in case the generation should be shifted from one side of the grid to another [139]. The ancillary services the Distribution System Operator requires for curtailment and re-dispatching are often imported from the Transmission System Operator since the Transmission System Operator already has a system in place to obtain those services [135].

5.1.4 Changing need for congestion management

The existing energy grid is designed to transport energy from centralised production units, with a stable energy output, towards customers with predictable loads. The transition towards more distributed and renewable energy generation, which has a higher production volatility, requires Distribution System Operators to react. [135] The grid is facing problems regarding congestion since the usage of the grid will change significantly. For instance, in the region of Galicia, Spain, the installed capacity of Distributed Generation operator connected to the distribution networks (2203 MW) exceeds the total peak demand of the area (1842 MW) [139].

To solve the evolving problems regarding congestion, reinforcing the grid to the level of the peak production and peak consumption is on many occasions not the most cost effective option, so the Distribution System Operators have to look for other options to ensure a stable distribution grid, while still connecting all new users to the grid. A solution to avoid or defer investments in network reinforcements can be provided by demand response. The EU-funded Improgres project demonstrated the benefits of demand side flexibility for the integration of decentralised generation. Another EU-funded project, MetaPV, compares the costs of a grid investment approach and a flexibility approach. The research showed that when the equipment price dropped or was shared with other services, flexibility usage became the most economic approach to increase grid capacity up to 100% [140].

Although the value of demand response in congestion management has been proven, there is no fully-integrated, interoperable and enhanced user platform to empower a cost-effective mass-market for prosumers, grid stakeholders and Distribution System Operators. There is a framework being developed to deliver a market model for the trading and commoditisation of energy flexibility -Universal Smart Energy Framework (USEF) [141]-, but this framework does not provide a platform for aggregators and Distribution System Operators.

5.1.5 Summary

The Distribution System Operators ensure the electricity grid in Europe is stable and accessible. To ensure a stable grid, physical congestion should always be avoided. In the traditional grid with large power producers and distributed consumption the most cost-effective way to cope with congestion was to reinforce the grid. However, due to Distributed Generation operator, the Distribution System Operators reinforcing the grid for the maximum power throughput, is no longer always the most cost-effective way. Demand-Response provides an alternative way of dealing with congestion, but there is no universal platform for prosumers and other grid stakeholders to provide Demand-Response to Distribution System Operators.

5.2 FAST DEMAND RESPONSE

This section of the report defines the emerging need for fast demand response (FDR) -also known as explicit DR-, as opposed to traditional DR -also known as implicit DR-, and provides a general overview of the current state of the art in implementing and using Fast Demand-Response. After the initial paragraphs which provide key definitions, the focus of the section shifts on identifying Fast Demand-Response resources in the modern grid and identifying characteristics which separate Fast Demand-Response from traditional Demand-Response systems. The second part of the section provides the bird's-eye perspective of the current state of the art in integrating Fast Demand-Response into grid operation, as well as several possible trends for the development of Fast Demand-Response which should be integrated into the Fast Demand-Response component of the DRIVe solution.

5.2.1 Traditional demand response

Traditional Demand-Response programs are related to longer term dispatch planning of the electrical grid. They are defined typically as price-based or incentive-based signals, forecasted during a time horizon in advance, where the main goal is to match the demand and supply of energy for the system, therefore involving exchanges between participants on the market.

This type of DR has received widespread attention and much research has been dedicated to this subject. More detailed technical surveys of traditional DR methods can be found in e.g. [142], [143] and [144].

5.2.2 The need for fast responding resources

Some events on the grid, however, need fast actions to avoid problems in the operation of that system, i.e. Fast Demand-Response. In bulk, at higher-voltage generation and transmission level, problems can be related to contingency situations, such as the sudden loss of a generator or a line, which can result in a situation of overload where generation and demand should be quickly balanced to avoid a general system black-out.

Resources that can be used in those situations provide ancillary services to the grid with response times typically under 10 minutes [145]. Several research studies on using Fast Demand-Response for ancillary services have been carried out, including frequency regulation and/or spinning reserve, such as [146], [147], [148], [149] and [150]. In these studies, Fast Demand-Response is considered especially useful in micro-grids, where there is no inherent inertia to smooth out power variations [151].

5.2.3 Fast responding resources on the distribution level

At the distribution level, the integration of renewable sources can cause several problems in the operation of the grid. One of them is the possibility of large power variations due to generation intermittency, that can disrupt proper voltage regulation and decrease the life-cycle of field equipment such as voltage regulators [152] [153].

While this has prompted solutions such as the development of fast Volt/VAR control systems (i.e. Processes for managing voltage levels and reactive power) with the use of power-electronics based compensators, researchers have also addressed the use of fast DR resources, e.g. buildings, chillers, datacentres, etc., for large-scale integration of renewables in the distribution system, e.g. [146] and [149]. Thus, Fast Demand-Response resources become another useful tool in the range of possible actions that Distribution System Operators can use to ensure the required service quality – not only in case of intermittency of renewables, but also for unforeseeable events such as fault conditions.

5.2.4 Significant differences of fast demand response

In contrast with traditional Demand-Response, Fast Demand-Response is not as heavily dependent on load forecasting as it is on very accurate measurements of the current power consumption and load shedding potential – i.e., the availability of the DR resource and the change of consumption from one instant to another [147] [154]. Therefore, the conditions for utilisation of FDR resources resemble more those of ancillary services than those of an energy asset [151] [155] [156]. In fact, a different category of DR for fast-acting ancillary service-like programs was created under the name of *Emergency Demand Response* (EDR) [150] [157].

The request for DR could be done via price signals or control signals. The latter seems to be a more convenient way for distribution operation, as it makes it possible to bypass the complexity of determining the proper price levels in real-time when facing time-critical contingency situations. In [146], direct load control (using the OpenADR protocol) is preliminarily evaluated for allowing the integration of renewable generation in the grid. However, [158] proposes a distribution-level fast Emergency Demand-Response for residential loads based on direct load control as well.

The command request from the utility typically goes to an aggregator, which in turn is responsible for sending the proper demand response commands to each individual resource [147] [159]. This aggregation pattern allows for implementation of distributed control approaches.

5.2.5 Implementations in practice

Notable examples of fast demand response are mainly implemented in the US. For example, Hawaiian Electric Company has a FDR program that requires energy use to be reduced within 10 minutes of event initiation, using automatic or semi-automatic controllers to act on non-essential loads [160]. Similarly, PJM Interconnection, a regional transmission organisation in the USA, has a DR program (Emergency Load Response Programs) that requires loads to respond in 30 minutes [161]. In the case of PJM Interconnection, curtailment service providers act as aggregators for retail customers.

5.2.6 Integration of fast demand response into grid operation

The integration of the Distributed Energy Resources into grid operation is another challenge to be addressed. Some of the considerations that need to be taken care of include the infrastructure concerns, such as the relation between the distribution operation platform and aggregators, means of communication and protocols.

Besides the infrastructure concerns, operational aspects of the integration should be considered, too. Goals in distribution operation include the control of grid voltage by means of utility-owned field equipment (voltage regulators, capacitor banks, among others), operated reliably when necessary. Fast Demand-Response resources need to be as operable as traditional utility-owned field equipment in the grid to become another resource for achieving distribution operation goals.

Apart from the manual operation of distribution asserts, there is also a potential application of joint utilisation of fast DR in Volt/VAR optimisation algorithms to manage voltage levels and reactive power. For example, in [162], DR is coordinated with other field equipment in an algorithm that uses a multi-agent system (MAS). Each agent controls a specific resource (loads, capacitor banks, regulators). As Demand-Response events happen, the information is automatically exchanged with other agents for proper volt/VAR control. On the other hand, in [163], authors include Demand-Response to deal with feeders on low-voltage regions by reducing local load instead of operating equipment with network-wide effects.

It needs to be emphasised that no common architecture for integrating DR has been identified in the existing references. For example, [164] presents one possible architecture for integrating Demand-Response into a distribution management system (DMS). In addition, advanced commercial Distribution Management Systems have already identified the need for a reliable, automated, local DR action [165], also integrated with Volt/VAR control systems [166] to manage voltage levels and reactive power.

If the fast demand response resources have ancillary-like contracts based on availability, then the complexity of their integration in distribution operations increases, especially if the load shedding levels are guaranteed and known in advance. However, if DR subscribers have the option to opt-out, if their load shedding levels can vary and are unknown beforehand, or if they are subject to price signals, then different types of forecast or statistical analysis might be necessary, possibly rendering their use impossible for short-term distribution contingencies.

5.2.7 Fast demand response resources

Based on the analysis of scientific databases, Fast Demand-Response resources is not a topic that has attracted as widespread interest of the research community as traditional demand response. Nonetheless, few interesting examples of research on Fast responding Demand-Response resources, i.e. FDRs, could be found in the literature, where Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning systems, datacentres and Electric Vehicle Charging Stations (EVCS) are identified as best FDR resources.

Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning systems are especially suitable for demand response as buildings can be viewed as energy storage systems in terms of thermal energy, being able to respond for a short period without compromising thermal comfort. In [159], the use of small/medium scale buildings, is discussed for FDR, controlling the air conditioning units. The requests were sent by the utility operator to the office buildings through an aggregator platform, using OpenADR protocol, where the “fast” label was applied to receiving a 10-minute notice prior to the activation of the service. In [167], a fast chiller DR controls strategy for buildings is implemented without compromising much of the users’ thermal comfort. The system is capable of curtailing power within minutes. References [148] and [168] also address the use of HVAC systems for FDR. Finally, in [169], a demonstration with OpenADR achieved response times around 4 seconds.

Another set of possible Fast Demand-Response resources are datacentres. In [170], datacentres are considered a great opportunity for delivering specifically fast and precise demand response services at the sub-minute scale. Datacentres are very energy intensive and represent an increasing proportion of electricity usage. In this application, the demand response capabilities of the datacentre had desirable characteristics such as safe controllability, extremely fast ramp rate and fine granularity (sub-kilowatt increments). Reference [171] specifically studies datacentres with varying workload to meet variable renewable generation. Finally, in [172], a datacentre is studied for providing fast regulating services for the system operator.

Another great potential for fast demand response comes from Electric Vehicles and Electric Vehicle Charging Stations, in a concept know as vehicle-to-grid (V2G), as the charging technologies involve power electronics and power flow can be quickly managed. For example, [173] provides a review on the utilisation of electric vehicles as a resource for ancillary services and integration of renewable energy sources in the grid. On the other hand, in [174], a Vehicle-to-Grid for distribution support implementation is done considering commercial Electric Vehicles and standard communication protocols.

5.2.8 Summary

In sum, fast demand response (FDR) systems may be defined as systems which deliver ancillary services in the power market and that can react to a control signal within 3 to 5 seconds, delivering their full power within 15 to 30 seconds upon receiving the control signal. The best-suited assets for Fast Demand-Response seem to be Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning systems, datacentres and Electric Vehicle Charging Stations; it seems that both the most common and the most suitable protocol for controlling these assets is OpenADR. Analysed from a long-range strategic perspective, Fast Demand-Response systems seem to represent one of the key requirements for making the smart grid reality and as such seem to be an emerging, currently under-researched topic in the scientific community.

Nonetheless, the current level of implementation of Fast Demand-Response seems to be non-standardized, fragmentary and limited in scope. Consequently, the actual, wide-scale implementation of Fast Demand-Response by Distribution System Operators in EU and at a global level is currently impossible as there still does not seem to exist a sufficient level of thorough know-how, detailed research, clear specifications, specialized standards and pilot sites which prove functionalities, benefits and resilience capabilities of FDR.

In that respects, inclusion of Fast Demand-Response into the DRiVE solution seems to represent a must, as a means of futureproofing it and making it aligned with the emerging trends in grid management. Fast Demand-Response integration, from that perspective, also represents a strategic opportunity for the consortium to propose clear guidelines and potential standards for using Fast Demand-Response.

5.3 CONCLUSIONS

Overall, the current optimisation techniques for distribution grid management are reaching a critical point where the proliferation of Distributed Energy Resources makes it increasingly difficult to assure grid stability, due to high production volatility, and installed Distributed Generation capacities that exceed peak demand and consequent issues with congestion management.

The only two solutions to this problem are either to reinforce the grid to new, projected levels of the peak production and peak consumption, or to avoid or defer investments in network reinforcements by introducing Demand-Response and Fast Demand-Response. The latter is by far the most cost-effective option, which represents the main justification for the DRiVE solution from the point of view of Distribution System Operators.

Moreover, introduction of Demand-Response into distribution grid management opens door for Fast Demand-Response, where fast responding assets, such as Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning systems, datacentres and Electric Vehicle Charging Stations, provide ancillary services to the grid with response times measured in seconds. In that respect, Fast Demand-Response is one of the key enabling technologies for the transition towards more, or even entirely, distributed and renewable energy generation. The introduction of Fast Demand-Response into the DRiVE solution can therefore be seen as one of the best ways to futureproof it and make it even more attractive to Distribution System Operators and Balance Responsible Parties, as well as to stakeholders and decision makers.

6 CYBER-SECURITY AND PRIVACY

6.1 SMART NETWORKS: AN ALREADY OLD TECHNOLOGY

Smart grids combine distribution networks and new information and communication technologies (ICT). These technologies allow collecting and consolidating information close to producers and consumers or during the energy transport and exploiting the information in a smarter way.

Contrary to a received idea, the network smartness is not a recent phenomenon. The first Supervisory Control And Data Acquisition (SCADA) systems appeared in the 1960s. Initially designed for supervising an industrial process, they have been upgraded to control them. For the first time, it was possible to remotely interact with the network instead of requiring a physical access on site. These Supervisory Control And Data Acquisition systems have been spread out rapidly in all industrial systems making their security a critical issue.

6.2 THE EMERGENCE OF NEW CYBER-ATTACKS

Supervisory Control And Data Acquisition (SCADA) systems have evolved through four generations. The last one is characterised by the Internet of Things (IoT). Despite their increasing importance, the security of these systems has not been taken into account since their conception, keeping evolving on weak basis in terms of cyber security. These systems have therefore allowed the emergence of new cyber-attacks aiming at destroying physically business facilities.

Since 2008, we have seen a steady progression in the severity and scale of those cyber-attacks on critical infrastructures. Everybody keeps in mind the Stuxnet case. Discovered in 2010, it was targeting Supervisory Control And Data Acquisition systems of Iranian uranium enrichment centrifuge, which lead to some damage and several explosions.

In 2014, a German steel mill has been targeted as well, when attackers have succeeded to take control of the production software and caused significant material damage to the site. It was the second time in history that a wholly digital attack caused physical destruction of equipment.

In December 2015, Ukraine faced the most important cyber-attack on a power grid: 700 000 homes without power during several hours. It was the first time in history that a cyber-attack on a power grid succeeded at a country level.

6.3 THE STANDARDS RELATED TO SMART GRIDS

Cyber-attacks are very diverse and their consequences can be disastrous. The best way to guard against them is to follow and implement the standards that have been defined in this objective. They are maintained up to date and profit from the experience of previous cyber-attacks.

Three standardisation organisms have built a coordination group (the CEN-CENELEC-ETSI SG-CG/SIG Smart Grid Coordination Group) and work on the specific topic of cybersecurity and data privacy for the smart grid. These organisms are the CEN, the CENELEC and the ETSI. The result of this coordination group is a report published in December 2016 entitled “Cyber Security & Privacy”. In this report, the standards have been divided into two categories: a first set of standards that defines the requirements (the “what”, see Table 2) and a second set of standards that defines the solution (the “how”, see Table 3).

Standard	Title
ISO/IEC 27001	Information technology - Security techniques -Information Security Management Systems –Requirements
ISO/IEC 27002	Information technology - Security techniques - Code of practice for information security management ISO/IEC TR 27001
ISO/IEC 27019	Information technology - Security techniques - Information security management guidelines based on ISO/IEC 27002 for process control systems specific to the energy utility industry
IEC 62443-2-4	Security for industrial automation and control systems - Network and system security - Part 2-4: Requirements for Industrial Automation Control Systems (IACS) solution suppliers
IEC 62443-3-3	Security for industrial automation and control systems, Part 3-3: System security requirements and security levels
IEC 62443-4-2	Security for industrial automation and control systems, Part 4-2: Technical Security Requirements for IACS Components
IEEE 1686	Substation Intelligent Electronic Devices (IED) Cyber Security Capabilities
IEEE C37.240	Cyber Security Requirements for Substation Automation, Protection and Control Systems

Table 2: Requirement Standards (The “What”)

Standard	Title
ISO/IEC 15118	Road vehicles - Vehicle-to-Grid Communication Interface, Part 8: Physical and data link layer requirements for wireless communication
ISO/IEC 61850-8-2	Communication networks and systems for power utility automation - Part 8-2: Specific communication service mapping (SCSM) - Mapping to Extensible Messaging Presence Protocol (XMPP)
IEC 62351-x	Power systems management and associated information exchange - Data and communication security
IEC 62743	Industrial communication networks - Wireless communication network and communication profiles - ISA 100.11a
IEC 62351	Security Protocol support for the Group Domain of Interpretation (GDOI)
IETF draft-TLS1.3	TLS Version 1.3

Table 3: Solution standards (The “How”)

All the standards considered in the report of the smart grid coordination group are in their last revision except for ISO/IEC 27019 whose last revision (ISO/IEC 27019:2017) was published 1st November 2017. However, the second revision of the draft, which has been used for the report, has not provided any significant improvement in the final revision.

6.4 THE SECURITY ANALYSIS PROCESS

The smart grid coordination group proposes a 6-step security analysis process for smart energy system (see Figure 8). The first step is focused on the Information and Communication Technology (ICT) architecture. Its main outcomes are the logical communication interfaces and the communication protocols used for the information exchange.

Figure 8: Security Analysis Process

The second step analyses the specific threats and impacts to the component and system functions providing risk level assignments to information assets.

Given the outcomes of the two first steps (Information and Communication Technology architecture and risk level assignments), the standard security requirements will be mapped during the third step whereas the standard security solutions will be mapped in the fourth step.

The standard security solutions found during the fourth step will be integrated into the Information and Communication Technology architecture during the fifth step resulting in a secure architecture.

The deployment details of the standards are provided during the last step, whose outcome is a set of interface specific recommendations for the security solution application.

6.5 FINANCIAL, HUMAN AND REPUTATIONAL RISKS INCREASED

To skip these design issues, the conception and deployment of the Smart grid could expose network operator of the smart network to three major types of risks:

- Financial risks: unreliability of service, system obsolescence by design, use of equipment for illegal ends;
- Human risks on critical infrastructure (cyberterrorism, shutdown by cyber-attacks);
- Reputational risks (theft of personal data).

Beyond these large-scale risks, Smart Grid technologies expose companies to other risks that can affect the reliability and security of the entire ecosystem, due to a variety of factors:

- Failure to take safety into account during the design phase: the majority of manufacturers design meters without including safety standards and norms, assuming that safety is above all the responsibility of the network operator.
- The risk of obsolescence in front of rapid technological change: smart networks integrate multiple and constantly evolving interconnected technologies, which represent so many vulnerabilities that can be easily exploited by cyber-attacks, and require even more complex security update management in response. In addition, smart meters must have the same lifespan as mechanical meters, but must also be able to demonstrate strong resistance to attacks. They must be remotely updated and easily patched to correct bugs or prevent threats and secure user data.

- Lack of applicable standards for security and confidentiality, lack of widespread good practices: however, standardisation of equipment is an essential factor for the development and implementation of Smart Grids, particularly due to the complexity of the material ecosystems and the diversity of actors proposing solutions.
- High dependency of systems on suppliers: the latter generally provide the entire system, with a multi-year maintenance contract where the evolutions are delicate, or even unimaginable (own-access technologies and deployments).
- Routing, storage and management of an exponential volume of data: data is essential information for decision-making in the development of smart power grids. Their good functioning and reliability depend on a fast and efficient processing of a mass of data.

6.6 IDENTITY AND ACCESS MANAGEMENT

The IEC 62443-3-3 security requirement SR 1.1 covers the identification and authentication of human users, as shown in Table 4. Such authentication is already required at Security Level SL1, but for this security level, group accounts are allowed to be used. For Security Level SL2, the required capabilities include that unique user authentication is available, e.g. through the configuration and use of individual accounts for each user having access to the substation automation system. There is no differentiation in the requirement for whether the user access takes place locally, or remote.

IEC 62443-3-3 Security Requirements	SL 1	SL 2	SL 3	SL 4
FR 1 - Identification and authentication control				
SR 1.1 – Human user identification and authentication	✓	✓	✓	✓
SR 1.1 RE 1 – Unique identification and authentication		✓	✓	✓
SR 1.1 RE 2 – Multifactor authentication for untrusted networks			✓	✓
SR 1.1 RE 3 – Multifactor authentication for all networks				✓
SR 1.2 – Software process and device identification and authentication		✓	✓	✓
SR 1.2 RE 1 – Unique identification and authentication			✓	✓

Table 4: IEC 62443-3-3 security requirement

With Security Level SL3, additional multi-factor authentication is required based on the SL2 capability of unique user authentication. Here, a differentiation regarding the location of the authentication is made, as SL3 requires multi-factor authentication for access through untrusted networks. This applies to remote access that will typically be performed through untrusted or less trusted communication infrastructure. Security Level SL4 in addition requires the capability for multi-factor authentication for all human user access to the system, so this would also apply to Human-Machine Interface or engineering workstations within the secure substation zone.

User Authentication

When looking at the different component types within substation automation, it shows that user authentication can in principle take place in a number of different places, and can be realized by a number of different technologies. Typical places where user authentication may be performed include

- Authentication at the Operative System level with standard Operative System level user accounts. Standard-Operative System based substation components commonly include Human-Machine Interface stations, engineering workstations, or remote access servers. They may also include standard-OS based station controllers.
- Authentication at the application level as part of an application account management. Such user accounts may be application specific, or may be integrated with Operative System-level accounts.

- Authentication at embedded devices. Such authentication is not common in current deployments. Hence, it may be performed instead remotely and indirectly through the corresponding engineering applications. In such case, the engineering application would handle the user account management at application level. Authentication between the application and the embedded controller maps to software process and device authentication covered by Security Requirement SR 1.2.
- Authentication at network devices, including switches and routers. In this device class, a common approach is to map users to roles (e.g. admin, operator, user) granting different rights on the components, instead of performing unique user management directly within these devices.

In the following, different realisation approaches are discussed for the example use case of local engineering access to an intelligent electronic device (IED) as depicted in Figure 9. The realisation approaches target Security Requirement SR 1.1 with a security level SL2:

Figure 9: Example locations for authenticating engineering access

Approach 1: The Intelligent Electronic Device (IED) itself may target security level SL2 and perform user authentication internally. Such realisation is uncommon in current Intelligent Electronic Device realisations. Furthermore, as there may be a substantial number of parallel Intelligent Electronic Devices within a substation deployment, directly performing user account management locally on each such device is not recommended from a security perspective as this would introduce a significant risk of configuration errors, lack of synchronisation, and unneeded user accounts in the system (conflicting with other IEC 62443-3-3 requirements like SR 7.7 – least functionality, or with secure maintenance requirements as identified in IEC 62443-2-4).

With such realisation, centralizing and unifying account management, e.g. through a central authentication, authorisation and accounting (AAA) server and backend protocols like RADIUS would be needed in addition. Other approaches for future consideration to address this issue, include the use of methods based on X.509 public-key and attribute certificates as described in IEC 62351-8 for use in the energy automation domain.

Approach 2: Engineering access to an Intelligent Electronic Device is performed through a corresponding engineering application that may perform unique user authentication of service technicians. With such setup, the authentication is not performed in the Intelligent Electronic Device, but on the engineering workstation where the engineering application is installed and from where users actually perform their engineering tasks. The application account management can also be integrated with the Operative System-level account management of the workstation, which would support centralisation of user accounts.

Approach 3: In cases where the engineering application does not support unique authentication at application level, the OS-level account management of the engineering workstation can be used as fall-back to ensure that service technicians are uniquely authenticated. A drawback with such approach is that in cases where it is required to trace former user activities (a capability required by security requirement SR 2.8), correlation of logs would be needed. The account activity (user login/logoff) would be logged by the Operative System account management of the workstation, whereas actions performed through the engineering application would be found in the application logs.

Software process authentication

From a secure system design perspective, authentication of communicating software processes across a potentially untrusted network infrastructure can typically be achieved in two ways:

- The communicating components, e.g. a station automation controller and the corresponding server in the control centre, authenticate each other through an authentication method integrated with the communication protocol itself, like the Transport Layer Security (TLS) handshake used within IEC 62351.
- Both communicating components are located within secure zones, and the communication between these zones is secured and authenticated. This is typically achieved through a secure IPsec based virtual private network (VPN) that can be established between the firewalls at the borders of the respective zones, or between dedicated appliances at these locations.

Considerations for remote access

Adding remote access capabilities, as shown in Figure 9, to a system typically introduces additional user accounts for human users to the system. Remote access solutions are based on different technical realisations and infrastructure. The following options may occur:

- Remote access components are within the scope of the target system. These components are subject to applicable IEC 62443-3-3 security requirements.
Example: a target system device may be accessible through an SSH connection. The SSH connection (conduit) and the remote device terminating SSH are within the scope of the target system.
- Remote access components partially lie within the scope of the target system. Applicable IEC 62443-3-3 requirements need to be met by those components within the scope of the target system.
Example: The remote access solution, besides external Information Technology infrastructure, uses an IPsec virtual private network (VPN) tunnel that terminates at the border of the target system zone -e.g. at the demilitarised zone (DMZ)-. The component terminating the IPsec VPN tunnel at the target system falls into the scope of the target system, whereas all other remote access infrastructure is defined external to the target system.

7 DEMAND RESPONSE STAKEHOLDERS AND VALUE CHAIN

7.1 OVERVIEW OF THE DEMAND RESPONSE MARKET

7.1.1 Types of demand response

To provide a complete understanding of the Demand-Response market in European Countries, it is important to differentiate typologies of Demand Response [175] currently available and used:

1. Implicit (or price-based) DR involves actions (e.g. load shifting or shedding) driven by costs. A typical example is the use of Time-of-Use (ToU) tariffs, which implicitly invites users to use appliances when electricity costs less;
2. Explicit (or incentive-based) DR occurs when a given user is asked to shift or shed appliances as a consequence of an explicit external request.

This difference is important since the market of DR is currently very different in the various EU countries.

7.1.2 Current market

DR services are growing in EU countries. While implicit DR is mainly driven by Time-of-Use tariff structures, which are now quite widespread throughout Europe, explicit DR services are currently available only in some countries and associated to participation in balancing markets (mainly frequency response) and peak management (e.g. Critical Peak Price - TRIAD in the UK).

Figure 10: Map of explicit Demand Response development in Europe today. Source: [176]

Figure 10 reports the current penetration of explicit DR services in European countries in 2017. Most of them are already active at commercial level (UK, Ireland, France, Belgium, Finland and Switzerland), while others are opening or developing preliminary services. To date, also Italy (closed in the figure) has established pilot campaigns to open the balancing market to Demand Response [177]; an update in the associated regulation is expected in 2018.

The value chains of implicit and explicit DR are different and involve different players, but in both cases require flexibility to be unlocked by DR technology providers. Figure 11 reports the theoretical DR potential in 2030, divided for the industrial, commercial and residential sector. This DR capacity potential strictly depends on the progresses on both technological and regulatory aspects [178], [179].

Figure 11: Theoretical DR potential in Europe by 2030. Source: [179]

DRiVe targets both the residential and commercial sectors, which has the highest proportion of DR potential. If fully unlocked, this potential could lead to approximately 135 GW of available flexibility in Europe.

While implicit DR has a direct use within the premises in which flexibility is unlocked, explicit DR depends on the schemes available in the country where it is deployed. Flexibility can be traded in energy, balancing and capacity markets and can be used to participate in dedicate schemes (i.e. CPP/TRIAD in UK). Figure 12 reports the market size for balancing and ancillary services in EU countries in 2015.

Balancing & Ancillary services (ENTSO-E's terminology)	A	B	DK	FIN		F	D	GB	IRL	I		NL	PL	SLO	E		S		N	CH	Total	
	MW	MW	MW	MW	GWh	MW	MW	MW	MW	MW	GWh	MW	MW	MW	MW	GWh	MW	GWh	MW	MW	GW	TWh
FCR	67	82	82	400		700	670	180	N/A	1.800		N/A	N/A	N/A			642		563	71	5	0
FRR	400	801	968	1.684		2.000	8.295	2.367	N/A	4.770	800	N/A	348		2.876	1.290		2.161	391	22	8	
RR	405	847		365		500		3.497	N/A	8.990	N/A	N/A			12.404	1.500		300	682	8	21	
Interruptible loads						1.394				4.061					2.050						8	0
Balancing market					0							N/A					1.600	2.000			2	2
Demand response						1.800						176									2	0
Capacity market															2.500						3	0
Other			200						7.046				4.980		14.979				392		13	15
Total (GW/TWh)	0,9	1,7	1,3	2,4	0,0	5,0	10,4	6,0	7,0	5,9	13,8	0,8	5,2	0,3	4,6	30,3	3,4	1,6	5,4	1,1	61,5	45,6

Figure 12: Market size for grid balancing and ancillary services in EU countries – 2015. Source: [180]

In past years, these markets have always relied only on generation side response and this is still true in countries like Spain, Portugal and Italy (closed to DR in Figure 10). Flexibility brought by load management is entering the same markets as competitor of traditional generation systems. Focussing on UK as advanced reference market for DR services, Table 5 reports the participation of DR (called DSR in the table) in the capacity and balancing markets and in TRIAD avoidance in 2016, as provided by OFGEM [181]. Response and reserve balancing services also include fast response services, as described in section 5.

Market	Total Market		DSR Participation		DSR Share of Market Value
	Volume (GW)	Value (£ Million)	Volume (GW)	Value (£ Million)	
2016 T-4 Capacity Market Auction	52	1,180	1.4	32	3%
Response and Reserve Balancing Services	NA	287	2.1	11	4%
Triad Avoidance	7	315	2.0	90	29%

Table 5: Demand Side Response Market (DSR) in UK – 2016

As reported, DR share of market value is still limited, but is growing and it is expected to grow significantly in the coming years due to the increasing penetration of Distributed Energy Resources and intermittent renewables and accelerated need for grid reinforcement, which will expand the market. As evidence, it is highlighted that at the end of 2016 there were already 19 aggregators registered as Commercial Aggregation Service Providers on the UK National Grid website, including three of the large six vertically-integrated suppliers. As further evidence, Figure 13 illustrates the expected global DR market for the period 2014-2023, with exponential predicted growth. At present, North America (especially the USA) forms the largest DR market in the world but the EU and Asian markets are expected to grow rapidly over the next 10 years.

Figure 13: Global Demand Response Forecast. Source: Demand response enabling technologies, Navigant Research

In the presented context, DRiVE has the potential to both unlock the flexibility of the residential and commercial sectors and use it to allow DR players such as aggregators to participate in existing energy, capacity and balancing market and in any established DR scheme.

7.2 STAKEHOLDERS INVOLVED

Figure 14 provides the high-level view of the stakeholders considered within the scope of the DRiVE project and that have a role in the DR value chain. The schematic also shows the connection between the stakeholders in terms of flexibility and data exchanges.

Figure 14: High-level view of the stakeholders involved in the DRiVE DR value-chain

Flexibility brings the value and connects all stakeholders within the chain. It is provided by end users, unlocked by technology providers/manufacturers and converted into services for both end-users and regulated and non-regulated players. Often the connection between stakeholders is bi-directional and multi-sided. For instance, prosumers are both providers of flexibility and beneficiary of associated DR services; Transmission System Operators are both providing DR schemes and benefitting from them.

The value brought by flexibility and DR can be expressed in economic terms. Implicit DR concerns only end-users and results mainly in cost-saving. Explicit DR involves the energy, capacity and balancing markets, so it provides revenue to all participant mainly in the form of sales and reduction of penalties for imbalances.

Table 6 includes a description of each stakeholder with indication of their role in the energy network and their value proposition/needs. This includes also the needs of end-users, whose description will be extended in section 8. The descriptions are in line with those provided by the Universal Smart Energy Framework (USEF) [182].

Stakeholder	Role in the energy network	Value proposition/needs
Distribution System Operator (DSO)	The distribution system operator (DSO) is a regulated player, which is responsible for the distribution of electricity at Low-Voltage and Medium-Voltage levels and must ensure high quality and cost-effective supply of electricity and maintenance and development of the grid. Due to the growing penetration of Distributed Energy Resources, its role is becoming more active, superseding the classical role of the Distribution Network Operator. Within the DR value chain, the DSO has a control role (in combination with the Transmission System Operator), but also an active role when it deals with local congestions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use Demand-Response to deal with local congestions and avoid curtailments of renewables; - Defer investments for grid reinforcement by solving grid issues with Demand-Response and still ensuring optimal and cost-effective supply of electricity.
Transmission System Operator (TSO)	The transmission system operator (TSO) is a regulated player, which is responsible for the transmission of electricity at High-Voltage level and for grid monitoring and real-time balancing of generation and consumption by deploying regulating, reserve and incidental emergency capacity. Additionally, it safeguards the long-term ability of the electricity network to meet demand requirements by planning reinforcement and extensions. Traditionally, balancing operations were performed by managing the supply side only and this is still true in many countries. In DR-ready countries like UK, Belgium and France, the TSO has already implemented DR schemes, i.e. has enabled demand side management in the balancing market mechanisms. In the DR value chain, it has a control role, but also an active role when it uses DR schemes to ensure the stability of the grid.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The TSO requires flexibility enabled by Demand-Response technologies to deal with grid balancing operations in a cost-effective way; therefore, it establishes dedicated Demand-Response schemes in agreement with the energy regulator and authorities; - The TSO is the main beneficiary of Demand-Response operations, i.e. it buys flexibility enabled by Demand-Response to guarantee the required grid capacity margins and balance it on a real-time basis. - Defer investment for grid reinforcement by implementing Demand-Response schemes on the top of classic supply-side management.
Residential user	The residential user is a consumer of electricity, but can also be a prosumer when it is contemporary consuming and locally generating electricity (e.g. with a PhotoVoltaic plant) and/or it actively participates in energy markets. Within the Demand-Response value chain, it is both a beneficiary of flexibility and the “enabler” of implicit and explicit Demand-Response services (he provides flexibility and benefits from the enabled Demand-Response services).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reduce the energy costs, and/or get additional revenue from sale of electricity surplus/flexibility through participation in Demand-Response schemes and energy markets; - Be more sustainable and have a more active role in the energy network; - Know more of his consumption and energy behaviours. - Keep and possibly improve its comfort conditions

Building/ Facility occupant/user	It works/spends time in commercial building (e.g. office, hospital, university, shopping centre, etc.) or industrial facilities, but has not control over the energy costs. However, it can provide flexibility for Demand-Response operation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Be more sustainable and have a more active role in the energy network; - Keep and possibly improve its comfort conditions; - Enhance the green footprint of the company it works for (when applicable)
Building owner	It is a consumer of electricity, but can also produce it locally. Like the residential user, it is both provider of flexibility and beneficiary of implicit and explicit Demand-Response operations. Unlike the residential user, it must both ensure comfort conditions for its workers/occupants and reduce impact of Demand-Response operation on the ordinary building operations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reduce the energy costs, and/or get additional revenue from sale of electricity surplus/flexibility through participation in Demand-Response schemes and energy markets; - Keep and possibly improve comfort conditions for its occupants
Grid- connected Renewable Energy Supplier	It is a producer of electricity, with plants connected to the Medium-Voltage or High-Voltage grid. For intermittent renewables (i.e. Photovoltaic and wind farms), when the size of the plant is typically higher than 1-2 MW _{el} , it must forecast and communicate the expected daily generation profile and then respect it to avoid the payment of imbalances penalties.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Minimise penalties due to incorrect forecasting of electrical generation; - Maximise revenue from participation in energy markets and from available incentive schemes.
Aggregator	It represents the central point of the DR value chain for it acts as mediator between the flexibility providers and the market. Its role is to aggregate flexibility (into portfolios) and participate into energy, capacity and balancing markets on behalf of its clients. The flexibility can be sold to the DSOs, the TSO, BRPs, suppliers based on the specific market and the established DR schemes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Extend its flexibility portfolio by adding residential and tertiary flexibility; - Reduce risk associated with dispatching of flexibility; - Maximise revenue from participation in DR markets.
Balancing Responsible Party (BRP)	The Balancing Responsible Party is responsible for balancing supply and demand within its portfolio of energy suppliers, consumers and aggregators. It holds the imbalance risk.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use flexibility to balance its portfolio and reduce the imbalance risk
DR Technology provider/ manufacturer	It develops and delivers Demand-Response hardware and software solutions for both implicit and explicit Demand-Response.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sell Demand-Response hardware and software solutions and provide installation, customer support, maintenance and other services.

Table 6: Stakeholders involved in the Demand-Response value chain – Role and needs

The value chain is also enriched by additional stakeholders who act as intermediate players and/or as support ones. Typical intermediate players are asset managers and district managers which act as mediators between end users, Variable Renewable Energy Sources suppliers and the aggregator; eventually they can also act directly as aggregators. Support ones include algorithms developers, hardware installers, consultants, Building Management System manufacturers etc. and also the regulation bodies which develop the Demand-Response schemes in collaboration with all stakeholders.

Finally, although not considered directly in DRiVE, the value chain also includes industrial sites and all the participants in energy and capacity markets (e.g. power generators, retailers, large industrial) when not already part of a Balancing Responsible Party portfolio. Their needs within the chain are a replication of those described for the Balancing Responsible Party and the various end users.

During the DRiVE project, efforts should be devoted to conduct communication and dissemination of DRiVE activities amongst the value chain players here identified. With respect to exploitable results accomplished within the project, identification of appropriate business models and definition of commercialisation plans should be carried out.

8 USER EXPECTATIONS

8.1 INTRODUCTION

The end users of the DRiVE solution are the providers of flexibility, but also the ultimate beneficiary of the enabled Demand-Response services. The category includes residential users and prosumers, owners of small and large commercial buildings and occupants of small and large commercial buildings. Belonging to the category, although not targeted directly in DRiVE, there are also owners of industrial sites and their occupants.

The difference between owner and occupants is relevant and it is not typically present in the residential sector, where the two stakeholders tend to coincide. The owner (or the facility manager or analogue role) of a commercial building has access and control over to the energy bill and is responsible for the comfort conditions of the occupants. It manages most the building/site assets and is the decision-maker for participation in Demand-Response schemes (either implicit or explicit). The occupants might have visibility on consumption, but have only limited control over building assets and generally this control is related to comfort aspects (e.g. local control of air temperature). However, occupants participate directly (when asked) or indirectly in Demand-Response operations for which the building/site owner opts in. In some cases, they might be rewarded for their participation in Demand-Response operations.

Each end-user tends to show different needs and expectations when it comes to Demand-Response. While building/ site owners are typically more interested in economic benefits (reduced bill, additional revenue, sustainable image for the company), occupants are more concerned about comfort conditions and on social aspects. In both cases, we see an acceptability issue, which involve technological aspects (user friendliness, data visualisation, etc.) and social aspects (positive engagement, continual improvements) and must be resolved considering expectations of both groups of users. The following paragraph provides an overview of the problem, which will be fully taken into account and developed during the DRiVE project.

8.2 KEY ELEMENTS FOR USERS ACCEPTABILITY OF DEMAND-RESPONSE SOLUTIONS

Unlocking flexibility to enable Demand-Side Response (DSR) will rely heavily on end users interest in taking up the technologies and concerns that come with it. For successful uptake, these concerns will need to be addressed to make sure consumers are at ease with issues surrounding flexible loads.

To assess user needs we first need to define who the intended end user is. In general, non-domestic users will require much more information and will be more actively involved than their domestic counterparts. Even within industries though, each user will have separate needs and different levels of acceptability of flexibility, so a customisable will be essential for mass uptake.

8.2.1 Domestic applications

For domestic applications, the system interface will need to be user-friendly, intuitive and easy to use. A graphical interface highlighting key data such as carbon and financial savings to highlight benefits and encourage continued use.

Much research has already been completed into domestic demand-side response with control being the largest perceived issue. Fell et al., [183] identified four main motivations for control:

- Comfort (such as temperature in the building);
- Time (in terms of consuming electricity as and when they need, not changing habits);
- Spending (a sense of control over bills);
- Autonomy (having overall control with no sense of external impacts).

The UK Government's Department for Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy (BEIS) commissioned a report from E4tech to explore the potential of demand-side response to 2025 [184]. The report explored consumer engagement with Demand-Side Response and while it concluded it was difficult to assess specific barriers due to the lack of current opportunities, research [185] found that 50% of respondents would take up a smart tariff if they were offered one. Most of those who were not interested gave scepticism and uncertainty over the impact of a smart tariff as their reason.

8.2.2 Non-domestic applications

Non-domestic users are likely to have facility or energy managers that will require granular detail for switching periods.

Element Energy prepared a report for OFGEM [186] which explored demand-side response for the non-domestic sector. The five main barriers in uptake highlighted were:

- Cultural/institutional (no view of the wider picture, multi-tenanted buildings);
- Negative perception (fear of negative impact of service levels, overstated benefits of Demand-Side Response);
- Economic (lack of financial incentives);
- Lack of technologies, offers or demonstration (Lack of offers and demonstration of safe and cost-effective operation);
- Complexity (complex agreements, balancing mechanism arrangements).

These motivations and barriers will need to be addressed at all stages of the project to ensure the end product is capable of meeting the needs of both domestic and non-domestic end users.

Other factors that will need consideration are:

- Easy implementation – no large or time heavy disruptions;
- Cost effective solutions – no big upfront costs or significant ongoing costs (servicing & maintenance);
- Give conservative estimations of benefits – what will be the minimum result? Can this be guaranteed?
- System should be flexible and easily over-ridden if needed, add or remove flexibility as required by the user;
- Displayed customisable information, dependent on who the end user is;
- Add or remove buildings and integrate;
- Easy integration with existing Building Management System;
- Daily/Weekly/Monthly reports to show savings both financial and carbon (and others?);
- Stability of electrical and heat supply.

The BEIS report [184] also considered non-domestic users and found that while there was a high interest in Demand-Side Response, barriers still remain. They split into four categories: cultural, regulatory, commercial (incentives), and structural (costs). The underlying theme of each is a lack of information and possibly incorrect perceptions of risks, costs and lack of benefit.

Users on all sides however will expect the system to fit in with their daily lives and operations, and not need to compromise on comforts or big changes in habits. It is clear that the current lack of information and understanding available is and will present a barrier to uptake of Demand-Side Response services.

9 USER ENGAGEMENT TECHNIQUES

Occupant influence on end energy consumption in the built environment and elsewhere has been documented in this report already (section 2). As technological advancements leading to higher efficiency plateau, occupant behaviour is likely to take on an increasingly important role in the coming years. Engaging users is therefore critical to the success of any deployed energy system.

User engagement is therefore a key step towards developing smart buildings, grids and cities. Engaging users in a meaningful manner, however, transcends simple visualisation of consumption patterns and includes customised views tailored to the needs of the user as well as undertaking an active effort to inform user decision-making behaviour.

9.1 USER ENGAGEMENT

User engagement refers to a human-computer interface, which relays some useful information to the end-user and induces a positive behavioural change. To do so, these interfaces have to move beyond simplistic and boring interfaces, which require the user to do a lot of work. This has been amply demonstrated in existing research where the need to move beyond usability aspects to active engagement has long been emphasised [187], [188], [189].

Nevertheless, and despite its importance, a formal definition of engagement has remained elusive. Multiple studies have defined it in terms of different attributes, for example presentation of information, user perception (of control, choice and usability), and feedback, which describe the physical, cognitive and affective aspects of user experience [188]. These aspects have been widely analysed in various contexts, ranging from search engines and video games [190], [191] to online learning and shopping [192]. User engagement can then be defined as, “a quality of user experiences with technology that is characterised by challenge, aesthetic and sensory appeal, feedback, novelty, interactivity, perceived control and time, awareness, motivation, interest and affect” [188]. This definition, despite its breadth, has been distilled from a wide-ranging literature review.

9.1.1 User re-engagement

A critical concept that has emerged over time is re-engagement which plays out on both short- and long-term time horizons. This is especially important because most services, particularly in the energy domain, are designed for multiple uses (i.e. a single user re-engaging with the designed interface multiple times). Aspects that have been identified as critical for this re-engagement to occur include convenience, ease of use, need for information and novelty. Furthermore, an initial positive experience influenced users’ likelihood of re-engaging [188], [193], [194].

9.1.2 User non-engagement and disengagement

There are two further aspects that need to be considered in the context of human computer interfaces. The first one is when users do not engage with the designed interface and the second is when they disengage. Both have been studied in some detail and show their own characteristics.

User non-engagement occurs primarily when users face barriers to becoming engaged. These range from psychological aspects most frequently experienced in web-based learning where users do not feel the social connection with the group. They can also be physical where users have reported online shopping experiences to be impersonal and stated a preference for physical shopping. Another reason which contributes to these is the lure of multi-tasking which leads users to not become engaged with any single service. These drivers are largely user-specific. Reasons which are not user-specific include poor usability (including information overload and too many options), cluttered or confusing feedback and the availability of (better) alternatives [188].

Even with engaging interfaces, users are prone to disengage after some time. This is not necessarily a bad thing as long as the disengagement is temporary and the users re-engage after some time. Reasons for **disengagement** have been classified as either intrinsic or extrinsic. Intrinsic reasons include loss of interest and physiological reasons to move on to other activities. Extrinsic reasons, on the other hand, include lack of novelty and interruptions in the environment and technological issues [188].

9.2 MEASURES OF USER ENGAGEMENT

It is a difficult task to quantify concretely what constitutes an engaging user experience. What makes one interface “better” than another? One common methodology has been to make use of surveys to compare different possibilities. This can take many forms but a popular instrument in research studies to compare different software as well as multimedia learning and training is through the use of Likert scale [195].

Detailed studies in online experiences suggest that user engagement is a function of six distinct factors: perceived usability, aesthetics, focused attention, involvement, novelty, and endurability [196]. Making use of this information has allowed practitioners to develop concrete surveys and questionnaires aimed at identifying the engagement potential of different interfaces.

A limitation of a survey-based approach is that it is only discriminative in the sense that it does not directly allow something better to arise from the survey. Likewise, the practitioner often has no real knowledge about the suitability of the users of the system, which might bias conclusions. With the emergence of truly big data, A/B testing can largely alleviate these concerns by smoothing out the noise. Other possibilities like Amazon Mechanical Turk have also emerged to recruit specialised users.

Some concrete metrics that have been identified and that might be useful to engage end users in an energy domain include [197]:

1. **Duration** measuring how many minutes / clicks the user spends on the interface actively before navigating away
2. **Learnability** measuring if the user changes his / her behaviour in response to information or suggestions provided by the interface; this includes both long- and short-term behavioural change
3. **Endurability** measuring whether the user re-engages with the interface periodically, occasionally or never after initial usage
4. **Usability and usefulness** measuring whether users can receive the data they need in an intuitive manner and if they make use of all the functionality provided by the interface

9.3 USER ENGAGEMENT IN AN ENERGY CONTEXT

As mentioned earlier, users are a critical link in the energy system. Historically, users – be they residential, commercial or industrial – can impact the energy grid in two major ways. One is their energy demand and the other is (peak) power demand. As we move into the future, it is important to reduce both of these by engaging end users and transition to a less energy and carbon intensive society.

As variable, intermittent renewable energy sources (such as solar PhotoVoltaic panels and wind turbines) provide greater fraction of societal energy needs, the supply side will become less flexible than it was historically. This means that both the demand and the grid itself will need to become more flexible to ensure security of supply [198], [199]. This is possible by mechanisms such as large-scale storage (through e.g. pumped hydro or industrial scale electrical or thermal batteries). However, this is arguably not the most cost-effective utilisation of societal resources. It is here that active user engagement presents itself as an attractive alternative.

9.4 ADVANCED METERING INFRASTRUCTURE

“Smart” meters, usually a misnomer for metering infrastructures that gather data at higher frequency than legacy devices, are a necessary component to garnering greater user engagement. The argument, and one that has been used in many countries to further smart metering infrastructure, is that greater visibility will bring about behavioural change. Yet, there exists no compelling evidence that data collection, on its own, will result in any change in user habits. What is required is an active effort to engage users to become responsible energy consumers [200].

Advanced metering infrastructure naturally forms only the first step in this activity. The next steps are to analyse the data but also present it in a visually appealing and comprehensible manner to a lay person. Finally, performance metrics, as discussed above and elsewhere, have to be implemented and tracked continuously to determine what works and what can be improved.

9.5 FROM SMART GRIDS TO SMART USERS

Advanced metering infrastructure is seen as a key enabling technology for smart grids to become operational. Smart grids, which will enable bidirectional flows of both information and energy, are seen as a necessary evolution to better align (possibly intermittent) supply with demand [201]. However, large scale data collection in smart grids of the future will enable service providers to not just match supply and demand but also to diagnose faults in the network and provide feedback to utilities and end customers. As mentioned before, the end goal in any smart grids project is two-fold: increase energy efficiency and decrease peak power demand.

9.5.1 Energy efficiency

Increases in energy efficiency can be obtained only through long-term commitment and behavioural change. As such, it requires the design of services, which motivate users to consume energy conscientiously and invest in products which have better efficiency ratings (e.g. lighting, transportation etc.).

9.5.2 Peak power demand

Decreasing peak power demand, on the other hand, can operate on multiple time scales. In times of exceptionally high demand, it is interesting to ask engaged consumers to reduce their grid usage. This is an instantaneous operation, which only happens infrequently. However, it is also possible that, peak demand is causing local problems for the low-voltage grid. The grid operator in this case has to invest in expensive grid reinforcements. Demand response, through engaging end consumers in a behavioural change program, can be a viable alternative. This can include changing cooking, heating or electric vehicle charging times but, in reality, is only feasible when demand-response can be managed automatically.

9.5.3 Factors influencing user engagement in smart grids

Projects involving energy users often have two specific objectives, the first is to better understand consumer decision behaviour and the second is to better engage them to facilitate the transition towards a smart grid [201] and perhaps even become energy prosumers. Studies have however demonstrated that user engagement is a multidimensional problem, particularly in the context of smart energy systems where an increased focus on social aspects has to be taken into consideration as well [202]. Studies have also shown that the most effective energy conservation strategies are those that include personalised marketing approaches [203].

These studies highlight the importance of providing every user not just with customised displays but also with providing them with societal signals to shape consumer behaviour [204]. Indeed, in a large-scale survey of over 200 projects annexed in the JRC report, over a quarter was identified to have a user-specific focus [201]. This detailed survey also indicated that projects investigating user engagement have been increasing in number (showing a 5-fold increase between 2005 and 2011). Furthermore, the overwhelming focus of these projects is residential users, while commercial and industrial users take the second and third place respectively. Unsurprisingly, Distribution System Operators and energy companies are the most active participants in these projects [201].

The user engagement component in these projects was identified to constitute the following questions:

1. Provide information about new technologies and applications;
2. Provide consumption data;
3. Investigate studies aimed at behavioural change.

These three questions taken together form a modular approach to engaging users meaningfully. Detailed analysis of occupant behaviour and engagement techniques has yielded a number of important factors. These are summarised in Figure 15.

Figure 15: Factors affecting user engagement with smart grids. Source: [204]

Among these factors, compatibility and understanding both improve customer engagement. Likewise, many users are more inclined in the presence of motivating factors such as reduced electricity bill and impact on the environment. Finally, user engagement can be hampered by perceived risks, which may be, in some cases, justified.

This analysis highlights the importance of promoting better understanding of services, as well as fostering a communal link to the electricity grid (power supply reliability). The former can be addressed by developing custom displays for end users which have been reported to lead to energy savings. These ideas have been developed further in [205] where the most important aspects of engaging with smart grid users have been identified as:

1. Personalisation: this reflects the customers’ need for customised information (e.g. in a residential perspective, users require data about the usage of their devices);
2. Gamification: this is part of a growing trend of creating connected social networks which participate in online “games” to encourage desired behaviour (in this case, energy efficiency or demand reduction); practical examples of such initiatives can be found commercially these days.

In addition, exclusivity and accessibility are two key concerns, whereby good behaviour is rewarded with positive reinforcement (exclusivity) and accessing / interacting with data is made easier (accessibility) [205]. The concept of gamification in smart energy grids has been further developed in [206] which is summarised in Figure 16.

Figure 16: A view of the gamified smart energy grid. Source: [206]

9.6 PRACTICAL EXAMPLES

There are a number of practical examples of user engagement in smart grids:

1. The design of a “social” smart thermostat in the UK has been detailed in [207]. The core focus of this work has been to investigate multiple user interfaces designed to interact specifically with users. This, they demonstrate, can lead to energy savings of roughly 38%. This is achieved by both informing usage and suggesting changes according to real time market prices, incorporating machine learning techniques. The use of machine learning algorithms allows the system to outperform a baseline controller. In this work, the learning User Interfaces were rated significantly better than manual User Interfaces, confirming that it is better to hide some complexity from the user [207].
2. Another practical example of engaging users has been the large scale LINEAR project in Flanders, Belgium. Findings show that with customer engagement in roughly 200 residential buildings, an average maximum increase of 430 W per household and a maximum decrease of 65 W per household can be realised [208].

10 CONCLUSIONS

In the traditional grid with large power producers and distributed consumption, the most cost-effective way to cope with congestion was to reinforce the grid. However, due to increasing Distributed Energy Resources, Distribution System Operators' reinforcing the grid for the maximum power throughput, is no longer always the most appropriate approach.

Demand-Response in distribution grids offers an alternative way of dealing with congestion. The value chains of implicit and explicit Demand-Response are different and involve different players, but in both cases require flexibility to be unlocked by Demand-Response-enabling technology providers. DRIVe project aims at designing and demonstrating a Demand-Response-enabling technology platform to unlock the flexibility of both residential and tertiary sectors and use it to allow Demand-Response players such as aggregators to participate in capacity, energy and balancing markets and in any Demand-Response scheme.

In this endeavour, progress will be made during the DRIVe project in several fields such as: access to assets in buildings, Demand-Response-enabling interoperability, cyber-security and privacy, smart algorithms, impact on the Demand-Response ecosystem and alignment with end-users.

In the first place, **energy-related assets** in the existing stock of tertiary and residential buildings are already controlled by local (sometimes fragmented) Energy Management Systems which range from basic energy control functions to more sophisticated performance optimisation but, so far, they hardly ever include connectivity with an additional intelligence in the Cloud. The introduction of the Internet of Thing paradigm through the conservative gateway approach (Local Energy Gateway) can provide these local Energy Management Systems with such a connectivity. From the Cloud, a Software-as-a-service Energy Management System (SaaS EMS) will govern building assets and enable them to participate in Demand-Response schemes by leveraging (and respecting) existing local Energy Management Systems. The keys for the success of this approach include:

- (a) enough interoperability of the Local Energy Gateway with the variety of communication protocols that can be found in the building automation industry (BACnet, Modbus, OPC, etc.);
- (b) limiting access to the most basic functionalities in local Energy Management Systems to gain remote governance of the building assets in a simple, predictable manner.

Demand-Response-enabling interoperability is another key point. In this respect, alignment with guidelines by the CEN-CENELEC-ETSI Smart Grid Coordination Group, Smart Meter Coordination Group and especially with the Smart grid architecture model (SGAM) model should be ensured. Although compliance with lower-level protocols above-mentioned will be adopted, research effort in definition of data models and use cases will probably be needed. EEBus is an open standard which proposes a universal framework for formulating use cases for interfacing with energy consuming or producing equipment and it should be used as guidance in this respect. Regarding the communication between the Local Energy Gateway and the Software-as-a-service Energy Management System (SaaS EMS), the consortium background already includes a proprietary protocol running on top of Advanced Message Queuing Protocol. Changes to this interface will be needed, at least to the data models and Application programming interfaces. Also, compliance with Universal Smart Energy Framework (USEF) definition of the market model and of the communication between the aggregator and the electricity market should be accomplished. In this respect, the consortium background includes:

- (a) USEF interface with Distribution System Operators for daily scheduling;
- (b) An interface with Transmission System Operators for Frequency Containment Reserve (FCR) services.

Both should be used as starting point, although changes might be needed.

Regarding communication of explicit Demand-Response control signals, the American standard OpenADR should be used as a reference, in the absence of an equivalent European standard. Furthermore, collaboration between OpenADR and Universal Smart Energy Framework (USEF) organisations is taking place lately, so attention to news in this respect should be paid.

Cyber-security and privacy will be addressed by designing and implementing cyber-security services according to guidance provided by the publications of the CEN-CENELEC-ETSI Smart Grid Coordination Group. Also, protection of personal data that may be involved in pilots must be ensured, in compliance with the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the corresponding local regulations.

Smart algorithms will be used in several domains. Forecasting techniques will be used in an innovative, hybrid approach using physics-based techniques at micro (building) context and Computational Intelligence-based techniques at macro (district) context for predicting load, generation and flexibility. Furthermore, existing Computational Intelligence-based forecasting algorithms will be extended to improve: (a) granularity and accuracy of prediction, (b) time steps and (c) execution speed for use in near real-time grid management. Model Predictive Control (MPC) techniques will then be based on day-ahead forecasting enabling the actuation of controlled assets at the most suitable time, thereby maximising Demand-Response (DR) potential. Next, the optimisation will be based on external control parameters (DR) and the knowledge of storage capabilities - a step forward from current Demand-Response approaches. Also, a Multi-Agent System approach will be introduced to address energy management at building and district level. An existing development based on Alternating Direction Method of Multipliers (ADMM) will be extended with new capabilities in order to govern the energy network in a decentralised and cost-effective way and allow integration of blockchain technology (more specifically NRG-X-Change) for payment transactions among participants.

To maximise DRIVe's **impact on the Demand-Response ecosystem**, efforts should be devoted to conduct communication and dissemination of DRIVe activities amongst the value chain players here identified. With respect to exploitable results accomplished within the project, identification of appropriate business models and definition of commercialisation plans should be carried out.

Finally, even when Demand-Response services are fully automated, it is acknowledged that they will also need **alignment with the end-user** in terms of expectation fulfilment and user engagement. Indeed, it is required an active effort to engage users to become responsible energy consumers and perhaps even prosumers. Emphasis should be put on creating clear and engaging consumer portal, by using techniques such as personalisation and gamification.

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